

UNIVERSITY OF LEICESTER

School of Management

Understanding the role of image building in the education industry: A study of
the image and perceptions associated with Applied Education/Vocational
Training

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for the Degree of Master of Business Administration

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by

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Applied/Vocational programmes have been a mainstay in Jamaica's education system for years. These programmes provide students with a myriad of benefits including employable skills, high employment rates, job placements and competence in different fields. However, even with these attributes, vocational programmes are perpetually marred with negative associations which cause a lack of interest and perceived inferiority for these disciplines. The aim of this study is to identify the associated images and ingrained perceptions that are currently associated with vocational education and training. Focus was particularly levied on understanding the effect that perceptions and perceived images had on the education industry and to discuss how the image building concept could be applied to counter the existing views in the field.

Since identifying the perceptions and images were essential components of the research, a phenomenological approach was believed to be the best approach for unearthing the requisite information. By using this method, the study was able to capture the rationale for vocational programmes' current perceptions as well as gain primary promotional insights on how to build the image of these programmes. After all the relevant information was collected and perused, they were used to gain a greater understanding into the role of images in education as well as inform the proposed research focus and sub-questions.

The objectives of the study were realized and unfolded one chapter after the other. The basis of Chapter 1 was to initiate the discussion on image and perceptions' impact on vocational education. To achieve this, pertinent information was given including a definition of vocational programmes, background to the study and the regional significance of the topic. This chapter also highlighted why this topic is of interest, and what was the ultimate aim of the project. Chapters 2 critically reviewed all the literature that was consulted to guide and substantiate the study. This included delving into theories and concepts that explain how images influence consumer preferences and decision-making. The myriad of concepts reviewed were aimed at dissecting the image building concept in hopes of understanding its structure as well as how these ingredients affected the education industry. They include: self-image congruence, self-presentation, the multiple-self as well as the attributes that influenced these factors such as symbolism and social expectations. The third chapter gave an outline of the employed data collection methods including the use of interviews and focused groups, the structure of the sample and the different steps taken to access the sites. More importantly, the

chapter also provided a justification for chosen methodology i.e. qualitative, as well as the rationale behind the specific qualitative method chosen—phenomenology.

The findings that were revealed from the research were highlighted in chapter four. This includes an explication of 11 core perceptions of vocational education produced from 64 different beliefs and views emanating from the study. Promotional insights for improving this arm of education were also divulged along with the preferred career options of the sample. Based on the analysis, it was evident that understanding how images affect consumers can provide useful insight in the quest towards image building in the education industry. Chapter five was the grand summation of the study. The conclusion confirms the relevance of image and perceptions in the education industry and how these aspects facilitate favourable brand image responses and programme preference. It also noted that without identifying and considering the role of images in promoting educational programmes, it could have an adverse effect on enrollment. Several limitations were also revealed in this section ranging from the small size of the sample to the shortfalls caused by the geographic distance from the research site. The recommendations that were formulated emphasized the need to position programmes to meet the various image requirements and also to focus on dispelling current negativities. The final chapter focused on reflecting on the changes, pitfalls and management lessons learnt from the study. It also provides explanations on how many of the research challenges were countered.

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CHAPTER 1.0

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to Study

In 2002, Jamaica along with other regional territories attended a workshop hosted by the International Labour Organization (ILO). Among the primary issues that were to be fulfilled was the development of a National Training Policy which among other issues would reduce the number of youth leaving school without a skill or qualifications and to increase the return for those post-secondary individuals that wanted to acquire vocational training (Gamerdinger, 2002). However, according to Gamerdinger (2002), this would only be possible through better promotion of the lifetime opportunities for work and income of their respective populations. The full expansion and promotion of vocational careers were seen as the primary means of achieving this objective.

Vocational Education and Training (VET) has also gone through a series of name changes and descriptions since becoming institutionalized. In its broadest definition, vocational education can be viewed as “a wide range of courses/skills that help students to prepare for entering employment” (Northern Ireland Assembly, 2008 pp. 1). It encompasses apprenticeship and technical education where the learner directly develops expertise in a particular trade or discipline through hands-on experience (Edward et al. 2008). The reference to hands-on experience is the key tenet of this discipline, as all other references emphasize the practical nature of this discipline including Career and Technical Education (CTE) and Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) and Applied Education. Since recently, the latter is the term that is being embraced by several other Caribbean territories.

1.2 Problem Statement

The learning systems that are now in place in many Caribbean territories including Jamaica are unable to address national and regional issues partly because they are created primarily to assist learners along tertiary and professional paths (Gamerdinger, 2002). As such there is limited emphasis placed on and interest in vocational training. Consequently, to change the current interest levels, these programmes must be promoted differently if they are to reach the maximum number of students and the targets they are designed to serve (Quinn, 1981). The problem is that vocational programmes have been deemed inferior since inception and

promoting it favourably would require more than just traditional marketing methods. It would need strategies aimed at building its image and altering the perceptions of the public.

The concept of image building is seen as the antidote for vocational education's image woes because its objectives can help to formulate and foster perceptions that would lead to an improvement in the image of the brand and programmes offered. However, the education industry has oftentimes placed limited emphasis on the ramifications of improper image transmission. In fact, while knowledge of how images are perceived and how they influence consumer response tend to dominate businesses and trading circles, these ideals have not yet transcended to the realm of education industry in the Caribbean. This is a serious concern because unless there is an attempt to understand the implications of the different images that exist, and an assessment of the factors that affect how these images are perceived then vocational programmes may find it difficult to transform its associated negative perceptions. As such, by attempting to shed more light on these issues the ensuing study will focus on using an approach which can assist in fulfilling these requirements i.e. the image building concept.

1.3 Purpose of Study

The research hopes to provide marketers with a deeper understanding of image building in the education industry. Additionally, the study aims to use this information to fulfill other motives, including:

- To understand the role of perceptions in influencing educational choices.
- To illuminate the marketing theories pertinent for the image building process.
- To gain insights from an important target on how to promote vocational education.
- To use the unearthed information to develop recommendations that can be used to augment the status of vocational programmes in Jamaica and the Caribbean.

1.4 Research Questions and Sub-questions

The main research question is to highlight the role that image building plays in the education industry, with specific reference to highlighting the image and perceptions that affect vocational/Applied Education programme choices. The sub-questions that were designed to address this topic are:

1. What is the public's perception of Applied/Vocational Education?
2. Does the perception of Applied Education pose a threat to its image building?
3. What are the preferred career options for students and parents and why?
4. What is the general consensus on the best ways of promoting Applied Education and how can these promotional insights lead to image building?
5. What if any are the changes needed to promote this discipline and how can these promotional insights contribute to image building?

1.5 Personal Interest

The concept of promoting vocational education (skills training) has been a passion of mine since youth. I believe that the intellectual capacity and finances that are needed for becoming Lawyers, Doctors Accountants etcetera, is only possessed by a few. The challenge however is that the other career options such as vocational professions are not viewed as esteemed or important as the ones mention. As such, vocational programmes are oftentimes undermined which triggers the widespread belief that only general academic programmes equate to success. This is a tenet that should not be allowed to continue. Therefore, I believe it is important that the image of vocational programmes be promoted in a way that augments its status as a viable career option.

1.6 Importance of the Research

This project is very important because it highlights the role that image building ought to play in industries that tend to overlook the relevance of such marketing activities. For instance, although academic programmes and institutions are at times viewed differently from major brands like Coca Cola or McDonalds, they all provide services that make them businesses. They also possess names or symbols, which are used to differentiate their individual offerings from those of their competitors, thus they too are similar to brands (Kotler and Keller, 2006). As a result, these institutions too ought to be mindful of their images. This dissertation will

therefore discuss programmes within the educational industry with a focus of understanding how they may be affected by perceptions and how these perceptions can be altered by image building. The information illuminated is crucial for marketers of applied educational programmes because unless these disciplines are seen as positive, they will not be fully embraced by prospective students. The information gathered from the study will also help marketers to examine the consequences of their marketing actions on image formation before campaigns are undertaken. Finally, the study's significance will help management to understand perceived images, their impact on brand preference and how this in turn can affect enrollment and bottom-line in the education industry.

1.7 Structure of the Project

The project is aimed at facilitating a better understanding of image and perceptions in the educational sector. The ensuing chapter (2) is very important as it provides a detailed analysis of all the extant literature and research used to substantiate the research claims. The key issues reviewed include the elements responsible for image and perception formation, the different ways perceptions and image affect programme choices and the marketing theories that were seen as relevant for an image building campaign, i.e. image congruity, image variations and symbolism. The third chapter explained the relevance of focus groups and interviews in collecting data, the rationale for the type of qualitative study employed i.e. phenomenology, as well as the overall framework of the data gathering exercise. Chapter four utilizes all the data collected and presents the findings and interpretations from the study. Finally, all the aforementioned elements were summed up in the conclusion and reflections chapters. These chapters addressed the lessons learnt from the study, recommendations for improving vocational programmes as well as the limitations of the study. Additionally, the reflections chapter also highlighted the management implications that were deemed necessary for image building to be successful.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The ensuing review hopes to focus on the role that images and perceptions play in the education industry and to address how these elements and the concept of image building affects vocational education. The discourse will try to achieve its objectives by first discussing the different types of images that affect the judgments and decision making of consumers. Secondly, the study will highlight the different perceptions associated with vocational education to ascertain whether the public opinion is wholly negative or whether new studies have elevated its status. The review will then transition to the impact of images on the education industry. Finally, a general summation will be provided which hopes to further elucidate how the aforementioned steps have contributed to a better understanding of the role of images and the concept of image building.

2.2 Overview of Various Images

The success of any product or service is largely dependent on whether the image perceived by the consumer is enough to trigger a favourable response towards the brand. Understanding image transmission is therefore the first critical step towards image building as it increases the likelihood of success. But what exactly are images and how do they affect the consumer's judgment? According to Kotler and Keller (2006), this can be answered by defining the term image, which is the manner in which the public interprets, makes sense of or perceives the brand, company and /or its goods and services. At the crux of this definition is the reference to one primary cognitive process that tends to affect consumer judgments, i.e. perceptions. Patterson (1999 cited in Silva and Alwi, 2006) embraces the relevance of perception and sees it as the consumers' view of the symbolic attributes and associations that possession of the brand affords (Patterson, 1999 cited in Silva and Alwi, 2006). In other words, certain images will be embraced and reap favourable responses by consumers because of what they grant. Therefore, successful images depend on how they are perceived by consumers.

Every consumer also has to contend with a variety of images all of which tend to affect how brands are viewed and embraced. This occurs because all variations of images play a vital role in whether a product/service is accepted and chosen. Jamal and Goode (2001)

confirms the relevance of these image variations and posits that how the consumers view the product or marketing activities (perceived image), how the consumer view themselves (self image) and the image the consumer wants to portray in the public sphere (self presentation), all influence consumer behaviour. Yet among the myriad of images addressed in marketing, one variation stands out as very important, self image/self concept. According to Jamal and Goode (2001), self image can be seen as the beliefs, thoughts and feelings an individual have of themselves. Understanding the idea of the self concept is thus crucial for the discourse on image building because the variations of the self image help to influence the consumer's decision making process and how images are perceived.

This idea of a self concept is multi-faceted and its multidimensional nature has been proposed by several psychologists and embraced by different marketers. Markus and Kunda (1986 cited in Aaker, 1999), endorsed the idea of the 'multiple-selves' and noted that the self concept can refer to any number of selves. Some of the notable self variations include: the good self, bad self, hoped for self, feared self, not me self, ideal self, possible self and ought self, all of which have their corresponding images that may be triggered at any time (Markus and Kunda, 1986 cited in Aaker 1999). Therefore, any impending marketing campaign must be cognizant of the multiple and present self categorized into the four core self images, actual self image, social self image, ideal self image and ideal social self image (Sirgy, 2000 cited in He and Mukherjee, 2007).

Apart from the variations of self images previously mentioned, there are also other images that tend to influence consumer decisions. Research has conceptualized other primary images crucial for understanding consumer habits including product image, brand image, corporate image, store image (He and Mukherjee, 2007) and perhaps more appropriate for this discourse, institutional images (Nguyen and LeBlanc, 2001). These images though diverse in name, have one thing in common i.e. they are based on how the consumer perceives and evaluates them. Brand and Product Image are based on consumer's perception and evaluation of the item seen (Sirgy, 1983 in Quester et. al 2000) whereas store, corporate and even institutional images are based on the individual's perceptions and evaluation of the symbolic and utility attributes afforded (Nguyen and LeBlanc, 2001; He and Mukherjee, 2007). Consumer perceptions are therefore undeniable, in fact, if a firm is evaluated and perceived as unfavourable, these perceptions can affect the images associated with the company and its products (LeBlanc and Nguyen 1996). The core tenet that exudes from the aforementioned images is that they are largely dependent on the consumer's view. What will

be seen in the next section is that consumer perceptions affect their decisions and influence how they behave towards the brands and the marketing activities. By recognizing how images affect the consumer, this will provide insightful details on image building.

2.3 The Role of Images on the Consumer

One of the most important image concepts that affect the decisions and preference of consumer is self image; the relevance of which is debated in various marketing literature. The common held view is that once there is no harmony between how consumers view themselves (self image) and the perceived image of a brand/product, the consumers will not be inclined to choose these items; a notion that came to be known as self image congruity (Jamal and Goode, 2001). The self image congruity concept has been used to determine the impact of images on product or brand preference, in particular, how consumers evaluate brands and how they make their final purchase or preference. According to Grubb and Grathwohl (1967, cited in Quester et. al 2000, pp 525), the self image congruity concept “links the psychological construct of an individual’s self concept with the symbolic value of goods purchased in the marketplace.” Bosnjak and Rudolph (2008) echoed similar sentiments but added that individuals will hold favourable attitudes and more likely choose those brands that match particular aspects of their self concept. Both insights have two key elements that are pertinent for substantiating the claims of the overall study. The first is the fact that symbolic elements are crucial for eventual decisions and two, perceived images need to match particular aspects of the consumer’s self concept. The first aspect is extremely important as it is believed that consumers seldom patronize or consume goods for their functional attributes but instead consume items based on their perceived symbolic images (Elliot, 1997 cited in Jamal and Goode, 2001). The idea behind this has ramifications for the education industry because if a vocational institution is perceived as being for slow students, a brilliant student may feel that such programmes are not congruent with his/her self image or self concept (Nguyen and LeBlanc, 2001).

Bosnjak and Rudolph’s (2008) reference to ‘particular aspects of the consumer self concepts’ has even more implications. As mentioned, there are several selves but equally important are the associated images that must be aligned to these selves before a favourable decision occurs. According to Sirgy (2000, cited in He and Mukherjee, 2007) there are four self image congruity types including actual self image congruity, social self image congruity,

ideal self image congruity and ideal social self image congruity. These differences in image congruence mean that the self has different modes of satisfaction and expectations. Therefore, decisions may be made based on the particular 'self' that the consumer or individual wants to appease and the perceived image necessary to make this possible. The self image congruence theory can therefore be summed up by affirming that once the perceived image of a brand, firm or even school is aligned with one of the desirable self images, the consumer is inclined to choosing such items (Nguyen and LeBlanc, 2001; Jamal and Goode, 2001; He and Mukherjee, 2007; Bosnjak and Rudolph, 2008). This can assist marketers in the educational field because if the images associated with certain courses and institutions can be promoted in a way that meets the symbolic requirements of the consumer or student, then a decision to enroll is more likely.

2.4 Significance of Image: A Theoretical Analysis

While the previous discussion of the self congruence theory does equip managers with insights into consumer behaviour, the concept itself is not sufficient to determine how images affect brand/product preference and decisions. The first concern emanating from the theory is the way it addresses the array of different 'selves'. For instance, with the existence of so many different selves and self images, how will a marketer know how to position their campaigns or products and how will these 'selves' and their respective image desires be triggered. According to Aaker (1999), this can be answered by knowing the dynamic nature of the self, which has respective impulses that can be triggered at any time thereby increasing the likelihood of several issues occurring. One such issue is the conflict that may emerge from the different self images especially in different situations (Aaker, 1999). To clarify this issue it was essential to fully understand the factors that determined the consumer's purchase decisions or preference. Aaker (1999) believed that these decisions were influenced by social adaptation where consumers needed to act and adapt to certain social situations prior to choices. Social situations are thus vital because they determine the appropriate behaviour the individual adopts in public (Cantor et. al, 1982 cited in Aaker, 1999). These are known as 'situational cues' and they dictate that certain social situations coupled with the consumers' expectation of how they should act, will determine an individual's behaviour and brand preference in public (Aaker, 1999). Therefore, marketers cannot focus solely on conveying products or images that are merely aligned with the consumers self concept, i.e. self image

congruity. Focus should also be levied on how consumers adjust their dispositional behaviour based on certain situations, i.e. situational congruity (Aaker, 1999). Both self image congruity and situational congruity brings into focus two key elements. One, the relevance of the link between product and self images and two, the importance of the social domain and how the consumer may want to present themselves in public. The latter will be subsequently addressed.

The self image the consumer wants to portray in public is another important aspect that should be considered to fully appreciate the role of images and the nature of image building. It is built on the premise that consumer behaviour is adjusted in light of self presentation because people oftentimes make purchases because of a desire to present one's self in a positive way (Aaker, 1999; Dahl and White, 2006). In fact, Dahl and White (2006) posits that, products and even brands can become unfavoured because they may depict an image that would deviate from how the consumer wants to be seen. The rationale behind the consumer's decision is equally as important. Products and brands can be assessed by both functional and symbolic means, but oftentimes consumers disregard the former and consume based on the symbolic attributes the item affords (Elliott, 1997 cited in Jamal and Goode, 2001; Nguyen and LeBlanc, 2001; Dahl and White, 2006). Therefore, both consumption patterns and self portrayal patterns i.e. using or consuming products to present the self to others also play a vital role in understanding the concept of self presentation (Sengupta et. al, 2002 in Dahl and White, 2006). Put simply, there has to be an emphasis on what these images mean to the consumer and how they want to be perceived by the public following consumption.

The concept of self presentation is also relative and has cultural implications to consider. In addition to symbolic attributes, consumption of goods are closely entwined with what is socially and culturally accepted (Quester et al 2000). What is socially and culturally accepted also affects how consumers view themselves and alters how they want to be portrayed in public. Triandis (1989, cited in Lalwani, Shrum, Chiu, 2009) also believed in the multiplicity of selves (private, public and collective), but noted these selves are based on cultural aspects. In individualist cultures like the USA, the private self is usually put before group interests, and emphasis is placed primarily on conveying a positive self image (Triandis 1989, cited in Lalwani, Shrum, Chiu, 2009). On the other hand, in collectivist cultures like China and Japan, the group interest is embraced and there is more emphasis on social acceptance and what others think (Triandis 1989, cited in Lalwani, Shrum, Chiu,

2009). Therefore, believing that someone will choose a product that runs parallel to their self image, i.e. self image congruity will not be enough to determine consumer decisions. They are also affected by their respective cultures. Hence, someone from a collectivist culture may respond unfavourably to a brand image that may depict vanity. In fact, it stands to reason that an individual may be deemed as a boast if the product that they purchase is seen by the group as being extravagant. As such, overly proud images and purchases may run the risk of relinquishing social acceptance.

Cultural implications also link directly to Lalwani and Shavitt's (2009) two social desirable responding theory. In individualist cultures there is a tendency to be more focused on the self, self aggrandizement and downplay what others think; traits which run parallel to the self-deceptive enhancement concept posited by Lalwani and Shavitt's (2009). Whereas collectivist cultures, like the ideals of impression management are concerned with what others think and focuses on group conformity and social acceptance (Lalwani, Shrum, Chiu, 2009). Nevertheless, even both have obvious diverging paths, they do have one common trait; they are all focused on conveying a positive and favourable image whether inflated, or simply to fit in. However, Bosnjak and Rudolph (2008) believe that the quest to solely convey a positive image is not enough to fully appreciate the overall impact that images have on consumer decisions. Pursuing positive images are merely approach motives to satisfy a particular self or social situation (Bosnjak and Rudolph, 2008). However, apart from the quest for positive images, there are also instances when decisions can be determined by the consumer's apprehension to avoid a situation or image, i.e. avoidance tendencies (Sirgy, 1982 cited in Bosnjak and Rudolph 2008). As a result, Bosnjak and Rudolph (2008) believe there should be more consideration given to the 'undesired self concept'. A notion which is defined as the least desired identity that an individual tries to avoid for fear of a bad or embarrassing situation ensuing (Ogilvie, 1987 cited in Bosnjak and Rudolph 2008). In other words, it is an outcome or negative self image that the individual tries to evade. The concept hinges on how distant an individual wants to be seen from their most negative or undesired self image (Bosnjak and Rudolph 2008).

The undesired self image has several implications for the self image congruency theory as well as the self presentation concept. Bosnjak and Rudolph (2008) believe that self image congruence fail to consider the complete cognitive variations of the consumer including their brand related beliefs. Put simply, each person is different some may pursue elements that provide positive images while others will detour from certain brands because of

the negativity they represent. Brand beliefs, perceptions and even brand associations may also cause avoidance for certain brands (Bosnjak and Rudolph, 2008). As such, poor market position may occur if strategies fail to find symmetry between the desired self image sought and the distance consumers want to be from their undesired self concept (Bosnjak and Rudolph 2008). Thus, unlike the self image congruence and self presentation theories which focus on seeking positive images (Quester et. al, 2000; He and Mukherjee, 2007), the undesired self image concept posits that consumers are more inclined to avoid consuming or being identified with negative images (Banister and Hogg, cited in Bosnjak and Rudolph 2008). The ensuing section will now provide a glimpse into the educational industry, in particular on vocational education. This area of education was highlighted because it provides an ideal example of how negative or perceived images can affect programme acceptance and enrollment. Hence, by using this example all the aforementioned arguments on the effects of images can be aptly applied.

2.5 Image and Perceptions of Vocational Education

Schools, like other services have programmes that can be adversely affected by the effects of negative perceptions and images. Vocational education in particular has different images that have given way to both good and bad perceptions. Those that lean towards the negative side have created one of the biggest impediments to the promotion of vocational education (Quinn, 1981). Perceptions such as the idea that the discipline requires little or no intellect have caused different reference groups in societies to steer brilliant or more academic students away from vocational programmes as the perceived image is deemed inappropriate for their aptitude (Quinn 1981). According to Quinn (1981), this impression has fueled other views such as, academic programmes being solely for ‘smart’ kids while vocational programmes being for students with lower aptitude. These sentiments are also widespread and typical of many societies throughout the world. In the Greek context, there is a common thought that general education or courses that were more academic were for students with a higher intellectual capacity, i.e. smarter, whereas vocational programmes were merely alternatives to house students that were slower (Le Blanc and Nguyen, 2001; Saiti and Mitrosili, 2005; Carole Millar Research, 2004 in Edward et. al, 2008). Therefore, there are perceived intellectual distinctions between students in theory-centered academia versus applied educational courses.

The aforementioned distinction is further manifested in the way students view tertiary academic institutions versus non-tertiary vocational programmes. Students now see the choice to enroll in tertiary based subjects as the benchmark, thus emphasis is placed on degree bound courses rather than applied subjects, as the acceptable and prescribed way to success (Mitrosili and Saiti, 2005; Song Seng 2005; Peckham, 2007). This causes a perceived distinction between vocational programmes and university status as well as pre-requisites for academic progression (Hodkinson 1999, cited in McCrone and Morris 2004; Mitrosili and Saiti 2005). This disparity owes its existence to other perceptions such as vocational education does not offer tangible or recognizable qualifications that can lead to worthwhile careers (Hodkinson 1999 in McCrone and Morris 2004). Therefore, vocational programmes were not only seen as inferior to college courses, they also lacked the social pedestal and had a 'dead end image' since their qualifications were not used as a pre-requisites for higher education. However, over time the aforementioned views on vocational programmes have changed. Though these perceptions have stained image of these disciplines for years, there have been notable improvements to how they are now viewed.

In the past, technical and vocational programmes were perceived as being more practical and primarily non-academic (Ivy, 2001; Charles, 2002). Today many believe this perception is eroding with many vocational-based institutions shedding their image and embracing more academic and oftentimes degree granting programmes (Ivy, 2001). Therefore, the mutually exclusive nature of programme offerings is now changing, with programmes and qualifications overlapping across schools. Vocational institutions are thus shedding the view of being 'dead end', and more like an option that can lead to good careers and tertiary qualifications. This new image has thus played an instrumental role in prospective students choosing different programmes because now there is a greater balance of prestige between university and vocational programmes.

The low interest for vocational programmes is also not entirely pervasive as some countries actually experience increased enrollment for these courses. Research in Australia shows an increase in the number of students gravitating towards these programmes, with enrollment moving from 60,000 students to 202,900 students between 1996 and 2003 (Dalley-Trim et. al, 2008). Additionally, the schools offering these programmes also increased from 70% in 1997 to 95% in 2001 (Dalley-Trim et. al, 2008). The Australian context therefore provides an ideal example that the preference for choosing general-based university education is also changing. In fact, Australia's Educational Industry provides other

startling contradictions for many of the perceptions associated with vocational training. Dalley-Trim's study (2008) revealed that many students opted to enroll in Technical and Vocational Training because there were several notable advantages of this discipline including good job opportunities, the prospects of acquiring a recognized qualification and the opportunity to do interesting careers. As a result, the information provides compelling arguments that refutes Hodkinson's (1999, cited in McCrone and Morris 2004) claims that such programmes were avoided because they were perceived as having no potential for a tangible recognizable qualification.

Finally, a major economic shift has also taken place in reference to the wealth incurred in vocational professions versus non-vocational careers. Initially, vocational courses were seen as solely for poor kids and one that would lead to meagre paying careers (Pimpa, 2007). Today some of Europe's most successful entrepreneurs attribute their wealth on humble beginnings in vocation. Evidence of this can be seen in City and Guilds' Vocational Rich List Table #1, where UK's Top Millionaires highlight their wealth made by various vocational-based sectors.

Table# 1: UK's Vocational Industry's Rich List for 2008,

Name	2008 Ranking	Wealth in Millions	Background
Sir Anthony Bamford	2	1950	Construction
William Haughey	12	260	Electrician
Jack Tordoff	15	210	Mechanic
John Frieda	20	190	Hairdressing
Andrew Creighton	39	85	Plumbing
Kevin Linfoot	23	145	Carpenter

Source: *City and Guilds (UK), 2008*

This revelation provides a huge boost for the image of vocational education especially in Jamaica where there is usually a misconception that VET careers have no future and little prospects for wealth. Nevertheless, even though the previously mentioned perceptions indicate a transition from the negativity usually associated with vocational training, evidence still show that applied education is still marred by negative associations. The following section will show how such images and perceptions can affect the industry.

2.6 Impact of Images on the Education Industry

Images are important elements when deciding on brands and educational preferences. The review has consulted a myriad of literature that has illuminated the multidimensional nature of images, the components vital for image building and the overall impact of images on consumer decisions. Therefore, for these elements to be successfully applied to vocational programmes, education marketers will need to consider the ramifications of self image congruence, situational cues and self presentation and the undesired self concept. This is crucial because as mentioned earlier, certain images will influence the choices students make when choosing their programmes (Hemsely Brown 1999, cited in Edward et. al 2008). This is because image that the student thinks they have, must be aligned with the perceived image of the course before they will choose such programmes (Foskett et. al 2003, cited in Edward et. al 2008). Hence, the subject or courses have to be seen in a way that suits the image of the prospective student before it is chosen. Therefore, if an institution or programme has an image of catering primarily to slow students this may affect a student who considers himself academically inclined. Understanding self concept is therefore vital for improving the image of vocational education.

On the other hand, self presentation also has a direct bearing on the marketing and image building of vocational education. Public portrayals are based on the need for the consumer/student to present their self image in a manner that is positive and oftentimes inflated amongst their peers (Sengupta, 2002, cited in White and Dahl, 2006). Hence, if vocational education is seen as being inferior to other educational programmes, prospective students may avoid it for fear of being associated with one of the aforesaid perceptions, i.e. for slow or poor students. Additionally, a student may avoid a situation that has the ability to convey a negative self image i.e. undesired self or stay clear of vocational programmes because of the groups or students that are associated with these programmes, i.e. dissociation (White and Dahl, 2006; Bosnjak and Rudolph, 2008).

2.7 Summation

Based on literature reviewed, conducting image building campaigns require identifying the various images that affect consumer decisions. This is an essential step

because in order for the images associated with programmes or brands to be positively altered in the minds of consumers (rebuilt), they first need to be seen as favourable. For this to occur educational marketers need to understand the perceptions associated with certain programmes and the meaning prospective students ascribe to these programmes (perceived image). This entails careful consideration of how students want to be seen (self presentation), the nature of their self images and the level of congruence that must be achieved if favourable responses are to be garnered (self image congruity). In addition, marketers will need to be cognizant of the elements that affect the aforementioned activities including the cultural and symbolic implications of programmes. By doing this it will ensure that marketing activities positioned properly to appease prospects; another step crucial to image building. The subsequent chapter hopes to discuss the instruments needed to extract the necessary primary data i.e. perceptions and perceived images associated with vocational education, to initiate the image building campaign.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter's aim is to highlight the methodological route used to collect the primary data needed to substantiate the claims of the study. The content will highlight the tools and steps that facilitated the main research focus as well as why these approaches were used.

3.2 Research Methodology

To fulfill the primary objectives of this research and fully understand the image and perceptions of the sample, a qualitative study was seen as more appropriate for obtaining the requisite primary data. Its importance is based on the ability to utilize a variety of methods focused on retrieving and interpreting critical data. From the data received, the researcher focuses on describing, deciphering or decoding the subject in question and gain a better understanding of the issue (Gilmore and Carson, 1996). This is vital for the current research because in an attempt to fully comprehend the image and perceptions associated with vocational education, individuals living this experience must be studied for their views and interpretations to be fully appreciated. By employing qualitative methods, it allows the researcher to see and understand the perceptions associated with skills training through the eyes of those experiencing it. The data revealed enables the researcher to see how other issues or influences may affect the phenomenon or topic in question (Gilmore and Carson, 1996). In other words, by providing the researcher with a reservoir of collected information, this will facilitate a better understanding of the research question focus. In addition, the approach also takes into account how humans decipher and give meaning to the world and objects, as well as how they associate meaning and interpretations to what is seen and heard (Vygotsky 1978, cited in Shotter, 2009). Consequently, because there was a need to understand the meanings and associations linked to vocational education, it was vital to employ a research methodology that had this capability at its core.

3.2.1 Justification for Methodology

Both Positivistic (quantitative) and Social Constructivist (Qualitative) methodologies have the potential to yield critical and useful information. They both capture data that can be used to assess or explain different research aims. However a qualitative approach was employed because its parameters and objectives are believed to be a more suitable data gathering option. This is because it compliments the research objective by unearthing and understanding the expressions, images, words and interpretations about the topic without the need for measurements (Ruyter and Scholl, 1998). Therefore, a qualitative approach was embraced as it provided the scope through which these human behaviours could be studied and applied to the field of marketing. A brief comparison of the two research methods as seen in **Table #2** gives a vivid example of why qualitative methods are more appropriate for this research.

Table# 2: Brief Comparison of Methodologies and Implications for Research

Qualitative Methods	Quantitative Methods	Implications for current research
Studies the views, opinions, experiences & interpretations individuals have of the phenomena (Hancock, 2002)	Concerned with the numbers and measurement of the topic (Hancock, 2002)	Numbers and measurement is of no significance for this study. To understand the role of image building in education it is necessary to identify the meanings interpretations and perceptions given by students that experience this subject. This requires a method that will unearth these cognitive associations. Furthermore, because the extracted data will be studied with little need for quantitative assessment, a quantitative approach would not be suited.
Seeks to delve into the minds of the individuals living the experience and	Answers or aims to ascertain how many people share a	This study is primarily concerned with seeing the phenomena through the eyes of persons involved in the experience,

aims to address why they think or attribute certain meanings to a particular phenomena (De Ruyter and Scholl, 1998).	particular view or how they rank their views. (De Ruyter and Scholl, 1998)	and from this identify why is it they feel that way as opposed to how many shared that view, thus a qualitative approach is more appropriate.
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Source: De Ruyter and Scholl, 1998; Hancock, 2002

3.3 Relationship to Previous Studies

The method chosen sought to capitalize on some of the limitations of the studies consulted in the literature review. Foremost were McCrone and Morris' (2004) report on the Impact of Pre-16 Vocational Education. Their study used similar data gathering methods as this project, including interviews and focus groups to facilitate data collection. Additionally, McCrone and Morris' report (2004) also focused on gaining an appreciation of the attitudes and perceptions of vocational education; an aim that runs parallel to this dissertation. However, they too concluded that more detailed accounts were needed from young people in order to facilitate the creation of strategies that would raise the awareness and motivate students towards vocational programmes (McCrone and Morris, 2004). Therefore, to fill this informational gap and build on the scope of their suggestion for future research, employing a similar yet more extensive methodological approach was believed to be essential for fulfilling the requirements of this discourse i.e. studying the image and perceptions of vocational programmes.

The other studies consulted used primarily quantitative approaches with most emphasis being placed on measuring data. For instance Pimpa's (2007) study was focused on identifying the factors contributing to the low esteem of vocational education. Although perceptions played a major contributing factor in that research, the aim was primarily on assessing the criteria students used to enrol in vocational programmes and to measure the importance given to each factor, thus a Likert scale option was used (Pimpa, 2007). Other researchers including Saiti and Mitrosili (2005) depended heavily on questionnaires to generate quantitative data. However, since the need for measurement and quantitative information was not the primary focus of this project, a deviation from the aforementioned approaches was deemed logical. The Literature Review also consulted other studies that were

focused on capturing feelings, attitudes and perceptions that utilized qualitative methods. However, where they differed was on the primary focus of the study. In fact, apart from Quinn (1981), there was no other study found, which addressed the promotion or image building process in education.

3.4 Specific Qualitative Approach

An array of qualitative approaches abound in the field of research, each capable of reaping rich informative descriptions and data. However, their respective applicability is dependent on the phenomena and context of the research. For the purpose of this research, the phenomenological approach was chosen. This methodology helps to expose descriptions that help in understanding the social and cognitive views of persons living an experience (Groenewald, 2004). It is only through complete discernment of these views that vocational programmes in its current state can be promoted in ways contrary to current perceptions. Furthermore, the phenomena has to be overtly described by those involved because without them the information or knowledge received will be fragmented with limited effect (Hancock, 2002).

3.5 Employed Methods of Data Collection

Divulging the essence of image building in the education industry required employing data collecting methods that were capable of unearthing adequate and relevant primary data. As such, the research used semi-structured face to face interviews and focus groups; two methods that were vital for realizing this objective. Both methods were also appropriate because of the geographic location of the research, the demography and the foreseen language impediments (patois). By using these methods, communication could be conducted in a manner that allows respondents to be more comfortable. In this case it would be done by mixing Standard English with their native language (Patois). Additionally, because semi-structured interviews involved open-ended questioning, the phenomena could be fully grasped by respondents, explored by the researcher and probed where discrepancies and vagueness emerged (Hancock, 2002). Therefore where clarity was needed, face to face interviews provided an approach that created more opportunity for the issue to be elucidated.

Focus groups were also used. This method complimented one key shortfall of the interview process i.e. fear of public speaking and shy respondents. The discussions assisted in allaying individual fears of public speaking and also provided an ambit where the voice of the intimidated individuals could be captured. The approach also provided a gateway into the minds and perceptions of participants because they were in their comfort zone. In fact, group interactions usually foster more communication and thus additional testimonies. This happens because once participants are among peers; they are more open and more likely to divulge rich detailed information (Hancock, 2002). However there is one essential limitation of focus group discussions that had to be considered in this discourse, i.e. biased articulations. In group memberships there is oftentimes a blanket of stress conformity (Terry & Hogg, 1996, Whittler and Spira, 2002 cited in White and Dahl, 2006). Thus to counter this issue each group was properly moderated and each member was drawn into the discussions through preliminary communication in their native language to make them feel comfortable. Nevertheless, the use of the preceding two data gathering tools was also an essential component for research in phenomenology. By using multiple methods of data collection it not only facilitated a more accurate picture of the phenomena, it also provides a better opportunity for factual and thorough findings to be revealed by virtue of methodological triangulation (Penner and McClement, 2008). Its relevance also became evident when the findings from both data collecting methods were synonymous and corroborated the data revealed within the literature review.

3.6 Data Collection Process

3.6.1 Sample Design and Data Analysis

The Montego Bay Community College (Montego Bay, Jamaica) was the location of the study. The institution had a population of 1350 students. The sample consisted of 28 students between the ages of 18 and 23, which means that the sample size was approximately 2.06% of the school population. For the purpose of the research, a non-probability sampling design was selected as the most appropriate means of acquiring the required information. This method then entailed a purposive approach in order to study students that fit particular criteria. Consequently, since the aim of the study was to examine the perceptions and images of vocational education, the study's purpose was to focus on the articulations of those that experienced this discipline (Trochim, 2006). Achieving this then warranted a criterion-based

sample method focused on choosing respondents based on certain conditions (Mugo, 2009). Therefore the emphasis was placed on choosing the participants that not only lived the experience but also on the ones who because of particular criteria would disseminate the best data for analysis. Hence to be eligible for this study each respondent had to meet the following criteria:

Criteria

- Age range: 18-25yrs
- Have experience in vocational education or currently enrolled in a vocational course.
- Must be willing to give their perspectives on how they feel or felt about the discipline.

The following graph shows the gender breakdown of the sample.

Figure #1: Gender Distribution of the Sample

Source: Montego Bay Community College (Jamaica)

3.6.2 Justification for Sample

The aforementioned age range was chosen because it was imperative that the sample had members that had already chosen or experienced vocational programmes. The average age of the Montego Bay Community College was within this age bracket so the selection was indeed logical. The criteria also called for members that had acquired the necessary

experience in the discipline as this was the core requirement of phenomenology. Thus to fulfill its objectives a complete extraction of the individual's views and perceptions was necessary. The third criterion required is indeed necessary for every research because without having someone to study, acquiring the essential primary data would be improbable. Fortunately, the students at Montego Bay Community College were ideal for satisfying these criteria. The institution had a wide variety of vocational courses, it had students that fit the aforementioned criteria and most importantly, it had students that were willing to articulate their experiences on tape.

3.6.3 Scheduling and Question Format

Once the intended criteria were solidified, the schedule and questions were further reviewed prior to traveling to the research site. Details of the schedule and questions are displayed in **Appendix B & C** respectively. It is however important to note that even though there was a pre-set schedule and specific questions for the intended research, the process had to be flexible as vagueness and discrepancies necessitated improvising and adding probing questions.

3.6.4 Research Access and Ethics

Site access protocol was observed prior to and during the study. Before conducting the research, permission had to be sought from the various gate keepers including the principals and school leaders of the following schools: Montego Bay Community College, Herbert Morrison Technical High School and the Career Development Institute all of which were located in Jamaica. However, only Montego Bay Community College responded and subsequently granted approval to conduct the required study. Details of the correspondence are shown in **Appendix A**. In addition, the intended sample was given the option of anonymity as well as the questions and scope of the study in advance. Importantly, the scope of the research had hopes of interviewing minors but this was aborted as most minors would not fit the criteria required for the sample. After acquiring all the necessary permission and approval, flight arrangements were made from the Cayman Islands to Jamaica. The research was conducted on **April 1st – 2nd, 2009** between 10:00AM and 1:00PM on both days.

3.7 Primary Data Analysis Process Explained

Phenomenological research is a task which entails meticulously combing through the respondents' articulations in order to interpret and understand their experience. To achieve this, the work of notable phenomenologist, Amedeo Giorgi was consulted.

The prescribed phenomenological steps emulated include:

A. Full immersion into the data collected. This required listening to recordings at least twice, transcribing the information then reviewing the transcription until a full appreciation of the content and intent was gained. Since the interviews were done in my native country of Jamaica, care was taken to ensure that the elements of bracketing were preserved and personal views and preconceptions were detached from that of the describers' experiences (Groenewald, 2004).

i. The data collection process involved three (3) focused groups and five (5) interviews thus representing one sample but eight (8) separate data sources. As such, to ensure manageability the transcripts were separated and analyzed individually.

B. Following this separation, the stage was set for the transcript analysis. According to Amedeo Giorgi this was referred to as familiarization (Castro, 2003). This was another review focused on identifying and appreciating the describer's perspective while understanding and contextualizing their intentionality and language (Castro, 2003). In other words, the reasoning behind the articulations was achieved. This step was crucial for the study because the language used by the members of the sample, Jamaican Patois (Patwa) had the potential to not only pose challenges for transcription but also interpreting the context of utterance. However, to counter this issue, the expressions were translated into Standard English in the exact context of their utterances and put below the actual articulations in a small red font.

C. The meaning units throughout the respective protocols were emboldened for identification. These units are statements, phrases or terms that possessed possible information about vocational perceptions yet still preserved the concreteness of the experience (Castro, 2003). This meant that the pre-suppositions and researcher prejudices remained separate from the meaning units, while the data remained raw (Groenewald, 2004). The excerpt below provides an appropriate example.

Rhonda: *It's sweaty, the floor everything that's not lady-like. Technically, that's not me.*

i. These meaning units were then labelled with meaning unit categories. Again, these descriptions are based on statements or phrases that referred explicitly to the vocational-based perception expressed by the participant. These divisions

however, still followed the intended flow of questioning so as to maintain the nature of phenomenology. Furthermore, when meaning units were explicit, headings were placed atop to delineate these units. An example of this is seen below.

Tiffany: Insufficient Remuneration

“It nuh degrading but no money nuh deh pon it”. (*its not degrading but it doesn't pay well*).

D. The individual transcripts were then summarized and discussed in reference to the meaning unit categories unearthed. This step ran parallel to Giorgi's transformation step where each protocol was changed into more psychological terms from 1st person singular to 3rd person plural, while still preserving the essence of the respondents' views (Castro, 2003). This process was conducted as follows:

- i. Each transcript was addressed separately.
- ii. The respective meaning units were rewritten briefly in more psychological terms to reflect the interviewees' core views by using the perception categories attached as guides.

E. The meaning unit categories were then clustered under themes based on common strands and fundamental similarities. The core themes were then illuminated by cross-examining the overarching meaning of the various clusters thus exposing the central theme of the respective meaning unit (Groenewald, 2004). A frequency of utterance graph was also formulated to show which perceptions required more emphasis during image building activities.

F. The findings were then interpreted to address the research questions and objectives.

The complete data analysis process is illustrated in **Figure #2** below.

Figure #2: Data Analysis Flow Chart

Formulated from Giorgi's Existential Phenomenological Research. (Castro, 2003).

3.8 Constraints for the Data Analysis Process

The Phenomenological approach is an extensive process. It involves working with the transcripts in a complete and unbroken format for research. The challenge is, these complete transcripts and other phenomenology steps tend to add to the prescribed word limit thereby compromising the remaining chapters. As a result, only crucial information were included in the body of the project while other pertinent data was placed in a labelled Appendix and discussed by making referenced to that location.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESEARCH FINDINGS & ANALYSIS

4.1 Introduction

The discussion of the data collected is the primary focus of this chapter. The information will be used to inform the main research focus i.e. “Understanding the role of image building in the education industry” as well as inform the sub-questions critical for understanding this topic. These questions are as follows:

1. What is the public’s perception of Applied/Vocational Education?
2. Does the perception of Applied Education pose a threat to its image building?
3. What are the preferred career options for students and why?
4. What is the general consensus on the best ways of promoting Applied Education and how can these promotional insights lead to image building?
5. What if any are the changes needed to promote this discipline and how can these promotional insights contribute to image building?

4.2 Data Analysis

4.2.1 Identification of Meaning Units & Categorization

Throughout the individual transcripts, the portion of articulations that possessed testimonies pertaining to Vocational Image and Perceptions were highlighted and then categorized as seen in Figure #3 below (also seen in Appendix F). The study unearthed 47 different core meaning units as shown in Table #3.

Figure #3: Example of Actual Meaning Unit Categories

<u>Esteem of Non-Vocational jobs</u>	←	Categorization
Mario:	←	The Lawyers and the Doctors are generally who people look up to so like in society they have a higher standard (<i>meaning unit</i>)
<u>Laborious</u>		
Anecia:		Labour Intensive.
Garcia:		HA! To stand up on my foot with a 16 hour day and damaging my fingers (<i>high pitch tone for emphasis</i>) (<i>alluding to cosmetology</i>).
Source: Montego Bay Community College. 2008 (Sample)		

Table #3: Meaning Unit Categories Revealed

1	Persons who like vocational education	25	Non-vocational careers are more trustworthy
2	Based on Strength	26	Not Ambitious
3	Better opportunities in university enrolment	27	Not for Women
4	Cannot Think	28	Lacks parity of importance
5	Class distinctions of various roles	29	Persons with little or no qualifications
6	Class Prejudices	30	Practical persons
7	Difference in income	31	Preference for Leadership roles
8	Difference in Prestige	32	Preference for Office Comfort
9	Dirty & unglamorous	33	Settling option
10	Suffer Discrimination	34	For slow learners
11	Esteem of non-vocational jobs	35	Doesn't measure up to society's ideal standards
12	For Blue Collar/Working class people	36	Some vocational careers are more relevant
13	For Patient people (time consuming)	37	Stationary
14	For persons without subjects	38	Disgraceful
15	For students in comprehensive schools	39	Time consuming
16	For those who lack literary skills	40	Unrecognizable qualifications
17	Lacks Income Potential	41	Vocational careers are given less responsibility
18	institutional class distinctions	42	Vocational careers are Recreational
19	Insufficient remuneration	43	Vocational skills are quicker to attain
20	Labour-intensive	44	Vocational students are less knowledgeable
21	Lacks Parity of value with University	45	Vocational students are more creative
22	Last option	46	Vocational students are more rounded individuals
23	Lower level qualification	47	Non-vocational careers are more esteemed
24	More prestige in non-vocational institutions		

Source: Montego Bay Community College, 2008 (Sample)

4.2.2 Summarization of Transcripts

To fulfill the objectives of Giorgi's phenomenological method, the individual transcripts were summarized to illuminate true meaning or essence of what the respective respondents were saying. The process was a necessary step in order to identify the dominant meaning unit within the individual transcript while cross-examining each meaning unit in the light of the topic under study (Castro, 2003). An example of a summarized transcript can be seen below, while the remaining summarized transcripts can be seen in Appendix 6.

Example of Phenomenological Transcript Summary

Focus Group #2 This cohort highlighted the relevance of future remuneration. The meaning unit categories that alluded to income potential were interwoven with other categories thus making it the most important perception of this cohort. The group also provided comparative accounts on the scholastic abilities of vocational students and academic students. They felt that vocational students were slower and lacked the aptitude to progress as opposed to academic students. The supporting meaning unit categories of these claims are: vocational courses are for persons who are not book smart and persons unable to grasp things or unable to think. Other meaning units that emerged highlighted the perceived future job expectations of vocational careers. The group felt that these jobs were stationary with little interaction. Parity of qualifications was also vivid as participants thought that vocational qualifications were not as established as university accolades. There was also a perceived distinction in the level of social acceptance of vocational careers versus university education. They felt that society accepted university professions more than vocational trades.

4.2.3 Exposition of Themes

All Meaning Unit categories that were linked or associated in any way were grouped, analyzed, and then thematized based on their common traits. The process include using the aforementioned steps to explicate the core elements or intention of the respective meaning units, then providing a composite description or theme that represented all the units of the respective groups. The individual meaning unit groups and subsequent themes can be seen in **Table# 4**.

Table #4a: Formation of Themes from Meaning Units

Themes	Meaning Unit Categories
A. Perceived Job Descriptions	Persons good with their hands and technical skills; Practical; Based on Strength; Hard and Stressing; Labour-intensive; Vocational careers do more work; Requires patience; For people who like it; Stationary and with little social interaction; Dirty/Filthy
B. Income Potential	Unequal pay with non-vocational programmes; Courses are chosen based on prestige and money; Difference in income; Insufficient remuneration; Vocational qualifications does not pay as much as university qualification; Vocational careers do have income potential; Unequal pay with non-vocational programmes; Preference for Office Comfort
C. Parity of Esteem	Difference in Prestige; Esteem of non-vocational jobs; More prestige in non-vocational institutions; Non-vocational careers are more esteemed; Non-vocational professions have a higher status; Stigmatized; Low Aspiration; Unrecognizable qualifications; Better opportunities in university enrollment; Lacks Parity of value with University; Not as established and recognized as university qualifications; Uneven qualification: Degrees are more important than certificates; University offers more recognizable and beneficial qualification; Does not fit into the typical progression of the education system; Non-vocational careers are more trustworthy.
D. Little Qualification	Persons with little or no qualifications; For persons without the requisite subjects to progress; No academic requirement needed for vocational programmes
E. Back up option	Back up option; Last option; Settling option
F. Aptitude	Cannot Think or grasp things easily; For those who lack literary skills; Not booksmart; For Slower Students
G. Caste Consciousness	Social class prejudices; Esteem of roles vary by class; Class distinctions of various roles; For Blue Collar/Working class people; Vocational careers are lower class; For students in comprehensive schools
H. Gendered Issues	Not for Women; Primarily for Men
I. Advantages of Vocational	Vocational programmes are for everyone; Vocational students are less knowledgeable; Vocational students are more resourceful; Vocational students are more creative; Some vocational careers are more relevant.
J. Unique Themes	Recreational; Responsibility

Source: Montego Bay Community College, 2008 (Sample)

4.2.4 Importance of Themes Based on Frequency of Utterances

Based on the formation of the themes above, it was also important to note which category was the most important so as to ensure more emphasis from future image building strategies. Figure #4 shows the theme entitled Parity of Esteem as the most frequently uttered. The results were based on the number of times the different themes were uttered during the interviews or throughout the transcripts.

Figure #4: Ranking of Themes

Source: Montego Bay Community College

4.3 Research Question Addressed

4.3.1 What are the public's perceptions of Applied/Vocational Education?

The vocational perceptions illuminated varied as evidenced by the different views shown in Table #4. As shown, there were 59 different views emanating from the study. These were then categorized into 11 core themes as follows:

1. Vocational Education Lacks Parity of Esteem with Tertiary Education

Throughout the transcripts there was a general consensus that vocational programmes and careers were inferior to university education and professions. One meaning unit category which highlighted this was:

- Vocational qualifications were less valued than university qualifications. This was also echoed by Song Seng (2005) who noted that the primary belief still resounding from vocational programme is that college/university is still seen as the only route to success as vocational courses lack parity of esteem.

2. Vocational Careers have less income potential

Difference in income and insufficient post qualification remuneration were very popular categories in the study. One meaning unit category that represented this perception was:

- Vocational careers experienced unequal pay with non-vocational professions. Students in expressing this sentiment went as far as saying that earning a substantial income is the primary reason for going to school and they would only go to vocational institutions if it paid better than university qualifications. As a result, the decision to choose university programmes continue to be motivated by the economic prospects and financial awards that are associated with non-vocational qualifications (Mitrosili and Saiti, 2005).

3. Vocational courses are for Lower Classes

Class distinctions and stereotypes were all clustered into caste consciousness. The perceived class differences between vocational and non-vocational courses were vividly expressed. This idea was also echoed by Pimpa (2007) who noted a correlation between socio-economic backgrounds and educational enrolment, with working class students gravitating albeit circumstantial to vocational programmes.

4. **Vocational Careers had difficult Job Descriptions** Majority of the sample believed that vocational careers were more strenuous than other professions. This was expressed by several respondents who all stated that vocational programs would only prepare them for roles that were

- **Ishana:** "hard and stressing"
- **Anecia:** "dirty and labour intensive"

Therefore, vocational education and careers still possessed the perception of being completely manual-based with knowledge gained only through strenuous physical means (Quinn, 1981; Saiti and Mitrosili, 2005; Pimpa, 2007; Edward et al, 2008).

5. **Applied Education is only students with little or no academic qualifications** The perception of vocational courses being suited for students with little or no qualifications was also rife throughout the transcripts. This was also perpetuated by the fact that vocational enrollment was seen as a last option, and one that required no formal education. Thus, it was believed that these disciplines should only be pursued if there was no other choice.

6. **Vocational Programmes are for students with Low Aptitude** Vocational students were viewed as having lower aptitude or lesser intellect than someone doing tertiary courses. These sentiments were shown with expressions such as

- **Jhanique:** "slow, not book smart cant really grasp things so easy like smart people"

This idea also fuelled other beliefs such as, only smart students should enroll in academic programmes while slower students without qualifications should stay in disciplines more suited for lower aptitude, like vocational programmes (Quinn, 1981).

7. **Applied Education are predominantly for males** Applied education courses were perceived as being an option primarily for men and bore characteristics that were deemed masculine. The following expression vividly articulates this view.

- **Rhonda:** "dirty, sweaty... based on strength... not lady-like"

Hence the ingrained perception was that the perceived laborious nature experienced in vocational careers was more appropriate for men because it lacked the softer more feminine features like being gentle on their "fingers". However, it is important to note the gender make

up of the sample. The study was made up of primarily women whose influence could have influence the view of vocational education being pro-male.

8. Applied Education and Careers are just for fun

Vocational careers were not viewed as a job to be taken seriously. If vocational programmes were done, it was merely to pass time. Therefore, one can deduce that applied education was not believed to be a serious career option.

9. Vocational Careers have less Responsibilities

Students of applied education were seen as aspiring to hold less responsibility in their respective career paths as opposed to non-vocational professions. Therefore, once vocational qualifications were attained, such students would be relegated to that of an apprenticeship with little responsibility and more servitude.

Apart from the negative perceptions conveyed about vocational education, members of the sample also expressed a few positive views on these disciplines. The positive elements that emerged were:

10. Vocational students were more creative.

11. It was quicker to start a vocational programme, finish and start earning a living versus other professions which required extensive studying before working.

The various perceptions revealed therefore confirm that applied/vocational programmes and careers still possessed images that were unfavourable to prospective students and the public.

4.3.2: Does the Perception of Applied Education pose a threat to its Image Building?

The perceptions that were uncovered about Vocation Education and Training (VET) will undoubtedly pose challenges for image building. The threats highlighted are multi-faceted and are based on a series of factors including the programmes' image of being inferior to general programmes. This in turn affects the degree of self-image congruence required to quickly augment its image. For instance, Hemsely Brown (1999 cited in Edward, 2008) believed that the image that a student felt they had, had to be aligned with the image of the course of study. The trouble with vocational education and careers as evidenced by Table #5 is that its image represents many unfavourable symbolic elements that students and the public

will not want to be associated with. In fact, Jackson et. al (1996, cited in White and Dahl, 2006) suggests that consumers will keep away from products, services or even entities that have negative symbolic implications or a perceived aura incongruent to their self image. Therefore, prospective students will act unfavourably to these programmes or even marketing campaigns aimed at building these courses thus undermining the image building process.

The perceptions and images of vocational education may further undermine the image building process because they may deviate from the way a prospective student wants to present himself in public. As affirmed by Lalwani and Shavitt (2009), choices made by individuals are based on the need for a specific self presentation. Consequently, students may opt for programmes or detour from vocational courses that have images that are deemed inferior or different from the self image they want to present in public. For example, one articulation from the sample posited that:

- **Mario:** "The Lawyers and the Doctors are generally who people look up to in society, they have a higher standard."

Therefore in an attempt to gain the coveted high standard of the aforementioned professions and be put on the social pedestals to be viewed as such, students may only gravitate to programmes that will enable transition into these careers. This affects the image building process because it will be difficult to build an image that has an established association of being lowly.

The promotion of the discipline would be a difficult task because of some of the perceived images illuminated. As noted by Weinberger (1986, cited in Andrews and Kim, 2007), the impact of negative perceptions and images is long lasting especially if the brand knowledge is rife and unchallenged. This is a vivid depiction of the issues that surround vocational perceptions since its associations have been pervasive and unchallenged for years. Thus uprooting a tenet that has been left unchallenged since its inception will result in marketing challenges. In addition, the widespread nature of vocational perceptions affect more than just potential and current students, these sentiments are also transmitted by influential reference groups (teachers, family and peers) who are oftentimes the main advisors of career decisions (Saiti and Mitrosili, 2005; Song Seng, 2005; Pimpa, 2007). As a result, the quest to reposition vocational education positively in the minds of the public will have to consider more than just the students but also the three reference groups that affect them.

4.3.3: What are the preferred career options for students and parents and why?

The information from the sample revealed a preference for seven major career industries as seen in Figure #5. This data was formulated from the frequency of career utterances during the respondents' testimonies. The careers that were alluded were Aviation (4%), Illegal Activities (4%) and Litigation (9%) rounding out the least mentioned careers. The professions mentioned the most were Accounts and Management (13%), Information Technology (17%), Business ownership (22%) while Science and Medicine was mentioned the most with 31%.

Figure #5: Distribution of Preferred Career Options

Source: Montego Bay Community College

The possible reasons for these career choices can be attributed to three primary elements: Economic Factors, Social Factors and Status. The quest for satisfactory financial rewards or above average remuneration played a significant role in the academic choices and eventual professions of many students. Payne (2003 cited in Edward et. al 2008) stated that most students actually based their educational choices primarily on socio-economic and symbolic benefits that the particular decision will provide. This means, if choosing a business or medical field will reap or provide huge pay-offs economically as well as in social standings, students may opt to enroll in these programmes. Evidence of this was rife in all eight transcripts as seen in the following excerpt:

- **Ramon:** "The people who make the most money in society are not the plumbers and the mechanics."

Therefore, one key reason for some careers being sought is for financial gains along with the fact that these careers have symbolic attributes that facilitate self image congruency.

Additionally, by affording this symbolic appeal these careers also embody the status the student wants to present in public. This is confirmed by one respondent who posited that:

- **Christopher:** "if you see a doctor, to everybody there is a certain level of esteem... while the mason (pause) they would probably look on him as a common man (commoner)"

What emerges from Christopher's articulation is that certain professions afford a certain symbolic value and esteem that attracts students. Therefore it can be said that because the prestige associated with being a Doctor far exceeds the image possessed by vocational careers, students may prefer non-vocational professions.

The career preferences may also be explained by understanding the influence images play in these decisions. Self image congruence is one ideal that may explain the rationale behind these career decisions. This is based on the fact that the perceived images of these careers are in alignment with the consumer's self image and because this occurred, students made these choices (Jamal and Goode, 2001). Additionally, it can also be argued that high esteemed professions such as the ones highlighted in Figure# 4 may have been chosen because they offer an image that allows the student to be socially accepted as well as be seen in a certain light. As a result, prospects may choose these careers because their perceived images are what society sees as ideal and an embodiment of success. For instance, one member of the sample expressed that:

- **Rashida:** "Like, everybody look up to somebody who is a lawyer and doctor but if you dress like a chef or waitress or something like that its not as [gesticulates with hands signaling high status]."

What is construed from the above articulation is that there is a desire to enroll in programs that will convey a high esteem publicly. Therefore doctors and lawyers as opposed to vocational careers like chefs will more likely stimulate more interest because of the high social image they provide. Again, the choice can be attributed to the symbolic elements that the careers afford. Moreover, the articulated distinction could also be based on the perceived symbolic elements bestowed on one set of careers versus another. This preference simply because consumers will oftentimes choose items because of the symbolic meaning that the

choice provides (Elliot, 1997 cited in Jamal and Goode, 2001). As such, because certain careers have the symbolic characteristics and may help us to portray the self image we want others to see publicly, these careers will be chosen because of the value that these choices will eventually bring (Sirgy, 1982 cited in Chang, 2001). Moreover, any deviation from this would result in the negative outcome parallel to the Self Discrepancy Theory. This tenet is very important in the career decision process because like the aforementioned respondents, students and consumers will eagerly try to meet the expectations of others; in this case, this would be a career that epitomizes success (Chang, 2001). If this is not done and a misalignment between how the student wants to be perceived and how they view themselves ensues, then a possible loss of social affection and acceptance is deemed imminent (Chang, 2001). It is little wonder why students may choose a career not because of what they like but because of what different reference groups see as the symbol of success (Song Seng, 2005; Pimpa 2007).

4.3.4: What is the general consensus on the best ways of promoting Applied Education and how can these promotional insights lead to image building?

(i) There were several ideas emerging from the sample for promoting and improving the image of Vocational Education and Training (VET) as seen in Table #5.

Table# 5 Articulated Suggestions for Promoting VET

Advertisements and promotions to dispel current perceptions
Campus Visits
Conducting special events and workshops
Customize the promotional campaign to meet the target group;
Educational programmes
Endorsements from successful industry professionals
Highlight exciting activities
Highlight income potential of vocational programmes
Market Research and insights from target groups
Practical workshops
Select targets based on low socio-economic status
Technical and Vocational intra-schools visits
Uptempo and upbeat promotions
Usage of Mass Media
Usage of videos
Vibrant Computer Graphics

Source: Montego Bay Community College, 2008

The information provided in Table #5 all fell into the realm of two major marketing activities, advertising and special events. Advertising was the primary option alluded to and its suggested purpose was to raise the awareness of vocational benefits and familiarize the public with positive factors that were frequently unknown. Pimpa (2007) also echoes this notion by emphasizing the need to highlight the benefits and prospects for vocational programmes following graduation. The reason for doing for this is to alter the idea that practical careers have no scope for financial benefits. Thus by promoting examples of persons who have benefited or earned satisfactory rewards, this would assist in eroding current perceptions.

The other core approach for promoting vocational education was by conducting special events. Quinn's (1981) opinion on the most appropriate special events for vocational promotions were Campus Visits, Tours, Open Houses, Career Days, Award Ceremonies and Vocational education week; all of which were aimed at raising awareness. The study revealed that the level of awareness needed to boost vocational programmes was not adequate thus the aforementioned events were imperative. Therefore, by providing such hands on experience or giving the public a taste of what is available in vocational training, this would ultimately raise the awareness of this discipline.

(ii) By aligning the image building considerations addressed in the literature review with the promotional insights articulated, this provides a greater appreciation for image building in education. The first promotional insight alluded to was advertising. The relevance of advertising to the image building debate is undeniable. Meenaghan (1995), considers this marketing activity as the core component of marketing imagery and image creation. Therefore, if properly used, advertising can have a significant impact on the creation or rebuilding of an image. Advertising would therefore be a key element for any image building campaign in the education industry as it can be used to highlight many of the key features which contributes to image acceptance such as symbolism. Thus, by highlighting the symbolic gains to be had in certain educational programmes, advertising can influence how these programme images are perceived (Mehta, 1999).

The role of advertising also affects the degree of congruence required to stimulate consumer interest, raise awareness and brand preference. Johar and Sirgy (1991 cited in Meenaghan, 1995), sees this occurring based on the two distinct persuasive strategies inherent in advertising i.e. utilitarian (functional) appeals and value expressive (image)

appeals. The former is synonymous with functional congruity and simply means that advertising may be effective by highlighting the practical/functional benefits the consumer considers important thus piquing interest and purchase (Johar and Sirgy, 1991 cited in Meenaghan, 1995). In other words, if a student merely had an intention to gain a Degree in Law, the main focus would be on providing academic and institutional options that offered this qualification. The value expressive (image) strategy on the other hand, being parallel to self image congruence involves formulating a brand personality or symbolic image of the product user that somehow appeals to the consumer (Johar and Sirgy (1991 cited in Meenaghan, 1995). Consequently, if the student had a self image of wanting to be a world renowned Lawyer with the prestige of being viewed as such, he would be more inclined to prefer a degree from the University of Cambridge or Harvard because they would be matched with the aura and image typical of these students. Both of the aforementioned strategies are useful for image building because they help to alter the perceived images of the consumer. Particularly from a symbolic perspective advertising helps to form the desired brand personality that would not only affect the brand images but also influence how they are received in the market (Meenaghan, 1995).

Conducting special events was the other option alluded to in the study that could actually be teamed with advertising to facilitate image building in the education industry. Like advertising, it can also help to promote brand awareness and stimulate functional congruity. Quinn (1981) also emphasized the need for several special events as a promoting tool for applied education including Tours to vocational institutions, Career Days, Open Houses, etc. These events provided the public with a first hand glimpse of what vocational programmes were about. To provide the feel and excitement, such events also provided hands on learning, a major activity that was suggested by the sample as being necessary for lifting the image of vocational programmes. In addition, Quinn (1981) also posited that special events actually raised the status of vocational education by acquainting the public with programme features, gaining the support of key stakeholders i.e. employers thus publicizing the attributes available in the field.

4.3.5: What if any are the changes needed to promote this discipline (vocational education) and how can these promotional insights contribute to image building?

Ideally, the element required for promoting Vocational Education is enlightenment and a change in the way these programmes are viewed. A comical depiction of this ideal manifesting is seen in Figure #6.

Figure# 6: Depiction of a change in the public's perception for Vocational Careers

Brown. (artist) 2006. Cayman Netnews Publication

Achieving this outcome requires a conscious effort by marketers to consider all the aforementioned image-based implications with an aim of positioning programmes symmetrically to realize the desired images. The first image consideration would be an attempt to achieve self congruence. As posited by Nguyen and LeBlanc (2001), self image congruence is a crucial element in the education industry because if student's perceptions of themselves are not aligned with programmes or institutional images then they will rarely choose such courses. Therefore marketers and administrators must change the way vocational disciplines are promoted. Educational services must understand the role images play in order to properly position programmes in the minds of target students (LeBlanc and Nguyen,

2001). Without this being done, image building becomes difficult because prospects need to see a positive image before they can be captivated by the respective image building campaigns. If marketers fail to achieve this self congruence then the brand images will be perceived unfavourably and will not be effective (Sirgy, 1982 cited in Chang, 2001).

On the other hand, educational marketers should also be cognizant of societal expectations, cultural influences and how these aspects influence self presentation. Throughout the study it was evident that the students' self presentation choice was influenced by what society considered acceptable and successful. For instance, as expressed by **Owen**:

"they (society) class the work that you're studying for; they're gonna class you"

From this articulation there is an essence of trying to meet societal expectations as well as embracing programmes that embodied success. In fact, Pimpa (2007), noted there was a correlation between manual jobs and low caste while Song Seng (2005), affirmed that vocational was not an epitome of social success. As such, because of such social scrutiny there is a quest to pursue careers that will enable the individual to present themselves more positively in public. Therefore, marketers need to understand how targets want to present themselves as well as the type of lifestyle that can facilitate this self presentation. Vocational marketers should thus try to detour from promoting the discipline as wholly manual-based and for low class children and use images and endorsements that will appeal to a desired lifestyle and public image of the prospects. In addition marketers also need to consider the impact of the undesired self images. Needless to say, based on the articulations of the study, vocational programmes already exemplify this undesired state. Therefore, marketers simply need to change perceptions such as; applied education is only for "slow" or "students not booksmart". This would require heavy investment and commitment in marketing activities that can alter current perceptions and brand associations such as advertising (Meenaghan, 1995).

Achieving the aforementioned changes is a feat that is indeed possible with the promotional insights articulated. Based on the information provided in Table #4, respondents highlighted the need for market research which could allow marketers to identify the desired self images and/or the public images sought. Campus Visits could also be used to show the fun-filled and interesting attributes available in vocational programmes while commercials and displays could be customized to attract targets. Advertising would therefore be the key

ingredient needed to fully augment the image of Applied Education Programmes. Advertising could be used to promote elements that foster greater self congruence, self presentation and ultimately facilitate decision making. One such element would be the symbolic attributes such as "highlighting the income potential" of vocational careers. By promoting these symbolic attributes, advertising can change the current perceptions of the discipline which in turn would influence how the brand image is perceived (Meenaghan, 1995). Additionally, because imagery and symbolism are inherent to advertising, the process would positively influence consumer decision by conveying associations that are congruent with consumer self images as well as the self image the consumer wants to present in public (Hong and Zinkhan, 1995 cited in Mehta, 1999). This in turn would allow education marketers to move steps closer to improving the image of vocational education.

CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSION

The primary aim of the research was to explore the nature of the image building concept and its relevance to the education industry. Fulfilling this objective entailed dissecting the primary building blocks of the image building process to facilitate a better understanding of its framework, its capabilities and elements that affected it. Based on the findings of the study, prior to building or improving an image, there has to be an appreciation of how these images are internalized and perceived by consumers. Understanding these processes are crucial for image building as they help to explain the changes need to foster image acceptance and brand preference. Within the education industry this is essential because it is only when a favourable programme image is fostered and becomes congruent with a student's self perception that such programmes are chosen (Nguyen and LeBlanc, 2001).

Perception is a major factor contributing to this outcome. This confirms the degree of influence perceptions have in school and subject preferences and it also calls into focus the wider framework of theories that influenced how and why these preferences are made. Among them was a tenet that resounded and was implied throughout the research i.e. the importance of self image congruence. Its relevance in educational programme choices was evident in the study and is thus a crucial component for image building in the industry. The premise affirmed was that in order to improve the images of applied education programmes, such programmes needed to be seen as favourable and match the self concept of prospective students. The other important theories that emanated from the research also corroborated the relevance of image congruence to the education industry and image building. They include self presentation, the undesired self concept and the multiplicity of self and its corresponding self images; all of which needed some level of congruence with prospects before preference ensued.

At the base of the aforementioned theories was another key element for image building i.e. symbolism. It was noted that because consumers are more inclined to gravitate to the symbolic attributes of a brand (Elliot, 1997 cited in Jamal and Goode, 2001) then it stands to reason that if educational programmes failed to convey some element of symbolism to attract students then self image congruence and the desired self presentation would not be achieved. This therefore confirms that for image building to be undertaken in the education industry, the images and aura that the programmes possess must exude an element of

symbolism before they can be perceived favourably and thus chosen. This notion was substantiated by the sample's rationale and preference for career options primarily because of the esteemed and symbolic attributes they provided.

The study has thus contributed to the breath of extant knowledge on image building. Although the focus of the discussion was on the education industry, the information lends itself to the role image building plays in the broader marketing context. Without understanding structural components vital to the image building process, one would be hard pressed to achieve a complete construct or improvement of a brand or product's image. Therefore by dissecting the structure of the image building process as well as its inherent ingredients, it is hoped that the essence of image building is clearer.

5.1 Recommendations

In an attempt to initiate image building and augment the status of vocational programmes, a few recommendations may be considered. The first recommendation would be to create a more comprehensive marketing communications approach by adding a public relations and publicity strategy to the activities alluded to by the sample. As defined by Kotler and Keller (2006) public relations and publicity are marketing activities created to promote and protect a company's image. This is essentially one of the main requirements for any image building strategy and it is a vital addition to the prescribed approaches alluded to by the sample. Not only is this mode of communication an effective image building tool, Hsieh and Li (2007) also see the process as important for enhancing brand associations and fostering positive brand attitudes and emotions. Consequently, if positive messages are disseminated about vocational programmes through public relations campaigns, this can help to alter many of the negativities that currently exist. Additionally, by using public relations in conjunction with other methods like advertising this would contribute to self image congruency by helping to project the image that the student desires (Herstein et. al, 2008).

Another recommendation that could be used to change negative images in the education industry is by apply a key element of Brand Equity i.e. Brand Revitalization. According to Keller (2003 cited in Schmitt and Gues, 2006), brand awareness is essential for creating brand images. Therefore, formulating strategies that will create awareness as well as revitalize the status of the brand is a logical step. Berry (1988, cited in Andrews and Kim, 2007) proposed a systematic approach to brand revitalization. The method called for several key steps including:

- An improvement in the existing quality of the brand;
- Understanding the reasons for the negative perceptions;
- Managing the consumer-brand relationship;
- Fostering and promoting a new attitude about the brand;
- Formulating a plan of action for the brand revitalization campaign;
- Initiating a grand re-launching event for the new and improved brand (Andrews and Kim, 2007).

The aforementioned steps provide marketers with approaches that are focused on alleviating negative perceptions while simultaneously promoting changes to how the brand is perceived. They show the relevance of identifying the current perceptions and understanding why they actually exist. Therefore, by illuminating the perceptions of vocational education, marketers can use this knowledge for image building.

Finally, whether it be the tools of marketing communications (advertising, special events, public relations) or strategies focused on improving brand equity through brand revitalization, one thing is certain and that is the importance of positioning. Marketers must identify the symbolic attributes that are of importance to the consumer. They must then try to appeal to either how the consumer sees themselves (self images) or how they want to present them self in public (self presentation). As such, image building campaigns must ensure that the programmes are promoted properly and positioned to appeal to the interest and perceived images of the customer.

5.2 Limitations of the Study

The limitations that emerged from the research revealed more than just potential gaps; they also provide possibilities for further large-scale research. These drawbacks are as follows:

- The first limitation was an unequal gender balance within the groups. The first two focus groups were primarily women and the second mostly men. Although the complete gender distribution narrowed during the face to face semi-structured interviews, having one overwhelming gender voice could have influenced some of the testimonies divulged.
- Another huge limitation was the overall size of the sample. The study sample was too small and thus limited the scope for generalization.

- The study perhaps failed to ascertain whether the divulged educational preferences were as a result of definite ambition rather than the process of image incongruence at work.
- The study should have also done more investigation into how the respondents viewed themselves (self image) and not just focus primarily of their perceptions (perceived image). This would solidify the true essence of the self image congruence concept.
- Finally, although Montego Bay Community College is an institution that offers vocational programmes, the study would have been more beneficial if it was conducted at a H.E.A.R.T TRUST NTA institution. This would provide complete immersion into the nature of vocational education.

CHAPTER SIX: REFLECTIONS

The completion of this project is a testament to the fact that what may initially appear insurmountable is achievable with perseverance. The road to this accomplishment however had several issues that could have been handled differently. First, although the methodology employed was appropriate, the nature of phenomenology was underestimated. The approach required an in depth, systematic process that had implications for the project. These implications included an emphasis on being extensive and thorough as well as constant reference to unbroken protocols/transcripts which ultimately compromised the prescribed word limit. However, these challenges were addressed by placing some of the less important steps in the appendices and making reference to that location during discussions. Additionally, though the presented steps mirrored the guidelines of noted phenomenologist Amadeo Giorgi, I believe that if additional mastery of the process was garnered the research would have been completed with less frustration.

There were also changes considered and made that differed from the proposal submitted. Initially, there was an attempt to change the research topic from what it is, to “understanding the perception associated with Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) and designing an IMC strategy to improve its image.”. However, the original plan was maintained as the changes would require a complete deviation from the proposal. But one question was slightly altered; instead of “what were the preferred career options for students and parents and why?” the inclusion of parents was omitted. This change highlights the relevance of ensuring that research focus and design are linked. The lesson was thoroughly learnt and fortunately the dissertation still fulfilled its objectives because the phenomenological approach was able to extract adequate relevant information.

Contrary to the research proposal, Jamaica rather than the Cayman Islands was chosen as the premier research destination. This was because within the Caribbean, Jamaica has the most established vocational training agency. Secondly, based on the nature of phenomenological research understanding how people lived the studied experiences was crucial. Therefore, since the Cayman Islands had limited vocational development, it would be more difficult to find participants who had lived or experienced this particular phenomenon. The study would also be more informative and beneficial if the research was conducted at one of the premier vocational institutions operated by the Human Employment and Resource Training Agency (H.E.A.R.T). The issue was that, although Montego Bay Community

College (MBCC) provided suitable candidates for the study, the school was primarily a general/more academic institution thus students may have been without the true sense of what it meant to be wholly enrolled in a vocational system.

Despite the aforementioned oversights, many lessons were learnt throughout the dissertation process. The information garnered will contribute to the field of marketing especially in promoting education, as little is known of the role of image building and perceptions in the vocational sector. I also feel that the information will assist marketers of vocational programmes in Jamaica to understand the relevance of image and perceptions in programme preferences.

6.1 Management Implications

The study revealed several important factors that will have implications for administrators and marketers of educational programmes. First, educational programmes are affected by the image-based elements that are typical of brands, products and services. The current discourse has confirmed the relevance of one such element, i.e. self image congruence, the effect of which is crucial for educational promotion. As such, the self image congruity concept needs to be embraced by marketers because the self perception of prospects plays a significant role in influencing their programme choices (Hemsely Brown 1999, cited in Edward et. al 2008). If they fail to achieve this congruence, the courses will be perceived unfavourably and will not be effective (Sirgy, 1982 cited in Chang, 2001). This concept also has implications for the manner in which prospective students hope to present themselves. Like brands, programme choices are also based on the need for a specific self presentation as evidenced from the study (Lalwani and Shavitt, 2009). Therefore, the desired images for self presentation also need to be taken into consideration. With both image considerations and others such as the undesired self implications to contend with, managers need to position their programmes to achieve optimal brand strength (Bosjnak and Rudolph, 2008). If this is not done, then programmes may appeal to some while negating the desired images of others.

The key concern for marketers is how to achieve the aforementioned desired images through marketing activities. This concern exposes key implications for educational marketers who must now place considerable emphasis on transmitting the symbolic attributes of programmes. The symbolic aspects facilitate image building in vocational programmes

because prospects need to be attracted to a certain image before perceiving it as positive. Consequently, symbolic emphasis has to be placed on programmes to first draw customers in then altering their perceptions and perceived images in the process. As such, merely promoting the utilitarian elements of institutions is not enough, symbolic/added value must be used to convey an image that will captivate prospective students (Jamal and Goode, 2001). With this in mind, administrators and marketers need to highlight such facts as the wealth potential of vocational careers so as to dispel current perceptions and raise the image of applied education.

Finally, because marketing imagery and image creation are core components of advertising, more capital investment and commitment need to be placed on this process (Meenaghan, 1995). By customizing advertisements with more symbolic messages, the process can be used to foster greater self congruence and desired social images which will in turn attract customers (Jamal and Goode, 2001). Therefore, by highlighting the symbolic gains to be had in educational programmes, advertising can influence how these programme images are perceived, thereby changing current perceptions and helping to building the image in the process (Mehta, 1999).

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Article Illustration (Figure #6)

Brown, C (2006) Blue collar jobs offer high earning potential.

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APPENDIX

Appendix A

Correspondence for Site Access

1. On Thu, Mar 19, 2009 at 9:50 AM, Atkinson, Ewort Ewort.Atkinson@gov.ky wrote:

Good Morning Dr. Samuels,

I am a past student of your institution, back in the days of Lorna Nembhard and Mr. Clarke. I am currently in the process of writing for my dissertation and would really appreciate your assistance. **Please see details attached.** I work in the Cayman Islands and hope to visit Jamaica soon to conduct the study, therefore, your swift response would be appreciated. Thank you.

Attachment

My name is Ewort Atkinson (*Jamaican*); I am a past student of the Montego Bay Community College (1999). I am currently enrolled in the University of Leicester School of Management (Distance) and I am in the process of writing my thesis for an MBA (Masters of Business Administration). My thesis research is entitled, "Understanding the role of image building in the education industry: A study of the image and perceptions associated with Applied Education/Vocational Training." In an attempt to get a student-based perspective, I humbly request your permission to enter your premises on March 31st, 2009 or April 1st, 2009, to conduct the relevant studies. The study will employ qualitative data gathering methodologies including, one-to-one interviews, unstructured interviews and direct observations.

Explanations

The in-depth interviews will include both individual interviews (e.g. one on one) as well as group interviews. The method used to capture the data in this method will be standard note taking and a recorder. The unstructured interviews will be more informal and will not be guided by pre-written questions. This will be achieved through casual conversations and the mode of capturing the data will be the same as above. Finally, direct observation requires a more detached perspective. Visual unobtrusive note taking will be carried out and this will be done in the most inconspicuous manner in vocationally based classes.

The questions I intend to ask are:

Questions:

- What is your career goal?
- How long have you had this career goal?
- What course are you currently enrolled in?
- What factors led you to choosing this course?
- Have you/did you ever see yourself being enrolled in a vocational course?
- Did anyone influence your career choice/path?
- Were your parents influential in your career choice?
- Which profession do you see as ideal and why?
- Who do you think is most suited for vocational training and why?
- What perceptions do you have of vocational education?
- Why do you think you have these perceptions of vocational training?
- Does vocational education have the same prestige as a university education, why or why not?
- What do you think accounts for the difference between university education and TVET?
- How is vocational programmes usually promoted?
- What message do you get when vocational training is promoted?
- What message do you get when university based programmes are promoted?
- Do you think the manner in which they are promoted help their image or works against it, explain?
- What message would you have to see to feel different about vocational education?
- What methods would you use to promote vocational training?

Observation

In addition to the above questioning, I will be observing the body language and facial expressions of the respondents as they may verbally convey one answer but their expressions may suggest something else. Therefore, small-scale probing will be used to ensure that the correct answer is illuminated. Based on the above questioning and other feedback, I hope to find out some of the reasons for the current perception associated with vocational education and see how best to customize marketing communications to further promote this discipline.

Target Group

The study will require respondents from the following programmes:

- Certificate in Food and Beverage Management
- Cosmetology Programmes Other Vocational Programmes

Quota required: 15-20 students

To satisfy the ethics requirement, students must be over the age 18years old or have their parent's permission

Importantly, the project and study activities will be explained in terms and jargons that each respondent can understand. This study is also completely voluntary; your student/child will participate only if he or she chooses to do so.

Confidentiality The information obtained in these studies will be kept with the strictest and confidence. Only the researcher (me) and the research and examining staff in the United

Kingdom will have access to the responses made by each respondent. For additional secrecy, respondents may also use fictitious names during recordings.

To further reiterate, participation in this study is voluntary. Your child/student's participation in this study will not lead to the loss of any benefits to which he or she is otherwise entitled. The study cannot be used maliciously and its confidentiality is the sole responsibility of me and the research staff at the University OF Leicester School Of Management. If your child/student agrees to participate, he or she is free to end participation at any time. The child/student is also not waiving any legal claims, rights or provisions because of participation in this study.

Date of Study March 31st and April 1st, 2009

Should you have any questions or desire further information, please feel free to contact:

Mr. Ewort Atkinson Student Researcher	Marie Petcher or Dr. Danziel Nurdilek
(Distance) University of Leicester	University of Leicester
School of Management	School of Management
25 Cumber Avenue BT	University Road
P.O. Box 30032	Leicester LE1 7RH
Grand Cayman KY1-1201	Tel +44 (0)116 223 1364
Tel# 1345-327-3030	Fax +44 (0)116 252 3949
	uslme fadv@leicester.ac.uk
	nd80@leicester.ac.uk

If you have any questions about your rights as a research subject, you may contact the University Of Leicester School Of Management by mail at University Road Leicester LE1 7RH United Kingdom, by phone at Tel +44 (0)116 223 1364, Fax +44 (0)116 252 3949 or by e-mail at uslme fadv@leicester.ac.uk.

I would really appreciate whatever consideration you give in allowing me to complete my studies. Please respond as soon as you conveniently can.

Sincerely,

Ewort Atkinson MBA Student (ULSM-UK)

From: Angela Samuels Harris [mailto:asamuelsharris@mbcc.edu.jm]

Sent: Monday, March 23, 2009 11:13 AM

To: Atkinson, Ewort

Subject: Re: Permission Letter (Montego Bay Comm C)

Mr. Atkinson,

The Principal has asked me to respond to you. She says that it is ok for you to conduct the research here at the college. However, she said I am to advise you that it would be during the time of mock exams. This activity she says has to be organised and therefore you would have to make the arrangements, that is, speak to the Heads of Departments prior to the time, select the students and circulate the documents to the students.

Regards,

Charmaine Miller

Appendix B

Research Schedule and Format

Date and Time of Research

Date	Time
April 1st, 2009	10:00AM - 1:00PM
April 2nd, 2009	10:00AM - 1:00PM

Format of the Research

1. Start with interviews: At least 15students in total Total time= 15minutes each x 15students = 2hrs and 25mins
2. Organize two focus groups of 5students=10students Total Time= 15minutes each=30minutes
3. Do five unstructured interviews with students around the campus. 5minutes each x 5students= 25minutes

Total Time= 3Hours and 20 Minutes

Appendix C

Interview Questions

NAME OF RESPONDENT :

DATE :

CURRENT COURSE OF STUDY :

EMAIL ADDRESS :

1. What is your career goal?
 2. How long have you had this career goal?
 3. What course are you currently enrolled in?
 4. What factors led you to choosing this course?
 5. Have you/did you ever see yourself being enrolled in a vocational course? Why or why not
 6. Did anyone influence your career choice/path? Why do you think they chose this one
 7. Were your parents influential in your career choice?
 8. Which profession or career choice do you see as ideal?
 9. Who do you think is most suited for vocational training and why?
 10. What perceptions do have of vocational education?
 11. Why do you think you have these perceptions of vocational training?
 12. Does vocational education have the same prestige as a university education, why or why not?
 13. What do you think accounts for the difference between university education and TVET?
 14. How vocational programmes are usually promoted in schools and in society?
 15. What message do you get when vocational training is promoted?
 16. What message do you get when university based programmes are promoted?
 17. Do you think the manner in which they are promoted help their image or works against it, explain?
 18. What message would you have to see to feel different about vocational education?
 19. What methods would you use to promote vocational training?
-

Appendix D
Age and Identity of Sample (Montego Bay Community College)

Focus Group #1

NAME	AGE	GENDER
Geleesa Robinson	18	F
Natasha Williamson	19	F
Anecia Pryce	23	F
Kaylia Harrison	18	F
Jon Hudson	18	F
Christina Reddie	18	M
Sanjae Miller	19	F
Mario Daley	20	F
Garcia Smith	21	M
Neocorla Duncan	20	F
Rhonda Williams	19	F
Tiffany Dennison	18	F

Focus Group #2

NAME	AGE	GENDER
Ishana Barnaby	18	F
Rashida Bernard	20	F
Shadacia Campbell	20	F
Jhanique Morrison	18	F
Christina Gordon	19	F

Focus Group #3

NAME	AGE	GENDER
Chad	18	M
Chin	20	F
Hustler	19	M
Antonio	18	M
Ramon	19	M
Reds	19	M

Focus Group #4

NAME	AGE	GENDER
Christopher Minott	22	M
Tamoy Russell	18	F
Owen Barnett	18	F
Lawrence Quarrie	19	M
Jason Gilpin	19	M

Source: Montego Bay Community College, 2008 (Sample).

Appendix E Transcript Example

FOCUS GROUP#1

Interviewer:

Alright just seeking permission. I'm going to be recording you guys for verbatim. When I'm finished recording you, I'll have to write out everything you say. Its not to be political its just for my research. Now, I graduated in 1997, no, 1999 from the Montego Bay community College. I did Pre-U.W.I. Arts at the time but I believe that having an Arts-based degree for instance going to UWI, its not really marketable. Alright so that is why I switched and now I'm doing an MBA through the University of Leicester. Now I currently work in Grand Cayman as a Programme Officer. In Grand Cayman, there is no sense of vocational training. There they import a lot of labourers for things like mason, electrician but none of the kids want to do it. So the thing is, when I was growing up I didn't want to become a mason either, I wanted to become a lawyer. Now why is this so? So that's the challenge I'm trying to understand. Tiffany, would you become a mason? Is it degrading or...

Tiffany: It nuh degrading but no money nuh deh pon it.

Interviewer: Yeah man! You can all talk the basis of this is to have a focus group discussion. What courses do you consider to be vocational?

Group: Architecture, Engineering, Food and Nutrition, Food Prep

Interviewer: Food Preparation

Group: Yeah and Cosmo Tech (Cosmetology)

Interviewer: Alright, question would you become a hairdresser by the way?

Garcia: I'm not good at hair so...

Interviewer: What are you good at?

Garcia: Cooking (group chuckles)

Interviewer: Hmm? Cooking? Oh! So would you become a chef or a cook lady?

Garcia: Yes but not as a day job

Interviewer: Ok...touch her, what's your name

Respondent: Natasha

Interviewer: As it relates to vocational courses lets say the plumbers, the masons ahh, who do you think these courses are more suited for?

Natasha: Males

Interviewer: So is it a gender thing

Group: Yes! Yes!

Anecia: No, No! Its not about the gender, or whatever but I think its for people who lacks Subjects, lacks literary skills

Rhonda: Like, the main reason why HEART was developed was geared towards persons who are not dunce but persons who were good with their hands. So they are more able to express themselves that way and they have good technical skills so therefore more able to advance.

Interviewer: I like the way you project, now I graduated from Cornwall with only one subject, so do you think my mother should have put me in a vocational course or do you think I was one of the type that was a slow starter?

Rhonda: Maybe it was because you were slow or maybe it was your choice to not do work.

Interviewer: Have you or did you ever see yourself being enrolled in a vocational course.

Ancia: I've enrolled in a vocational course

Garcia: I've done one...I've done two

Interviewer: Which one...which two have you done

Garcia: Cosmetology and Front Office

Interviewer: So why didn't you continue in cosmetology?

Garcia: Cause that's not my area (laughs) I didn't want to do it I just wanted to do it for fun.

Interviewer: So what do you consider as your area?

Garcia: Managerial (group laughs)

Interviewer: Now, am question, why managerial jobs by he way?

Garcia: Because I think I'm a good leader

Interviewer: So cant you be like a lead plumber or lead cosmetologist?

Garcia: Ahh! I could but if I was going to do like Chemistry, but I don't like Chemistry therefore, I'm not going to go to school for it.

Interviewer: Mr. Cornwallian, which profession do you see as ideal?

Mario: The Lawyers and the Doctors are generally who people look up to so like in society they have a higher standard.

Interviewer: What perceptions do you have of vocational courses (Group laughs) like a mason, plumber, electricians, what do you think of them?

Rhonda: You know (thought) because as we said its for persons who may not be so advanced, what we say verbally or on paper.

Interviewer: What do you honestly think of manual or non-office careers like vocational courses?

Jon: It's based on strength

Ancia: Labour intensive

Garcia: HA! To stand up on my foot with a 16 hour day and damaging my fingers (*high pitch tone for emphasis*) (alluding to cosmetology)

Interviewer: What if you owned the salon?

Garcia: If I owned the salon*(strong tone)*, I'd be employing (*strong tone*) people to work.

Interviewer: You'd be the manager?

Garcia: Exactly! (*strong tone*) So I'd be in the OFFICE (*high tone*) under AC watching them do MY WORK. (Group: Laughs)

Interviewer: Would you prefer to go to university and get an academic based degree or go to HEART and get hands on competence degree?

Sanjae: It depends!

Interviewer: It depends on what?

Sanjae: On the pay and the work you have to put in because I'm now doing a litt...I would say bookwork and it's very hard. If I could go to HEART and get...lets say more money (*high pitch for emphasis*) than what I'm going to get now then sure I'd (*high pitch for emphasis*) do it!

Interviewer: Anybody here wants to own their own business?

Group: Yeah! (All raise hands)

Anecia: Everybody basically.

Interviewer: So why not open a garage?

Rhonda: Dirty Fingers!

Interviewer: Dirty fingers, proceed

Rhonda: (with the help of group) Its sweaty, the floor everything that's not lady-like. Technically, that's not me.

Interviewer: Ok. What do you think accounts for the difference between a university education and the education from HEART? Why is there a difference?

Anecia: Society's Standards!

Interviewer: (group member showing a look of disagreement) You disagree?

Christina: SOCIOLOGY-BASED, its me, how we start off again? If we make the choice of going to university that's like going spending my time and money to go to university. I want to benefit from that but if I'm going to HEART, you don't pay much money and things like that. I don't think (pause) you're going to get the same amount of pay. You don't get the same amount of pay.

Rhonda: They do pay a lot of money. The issue is according to her is SOCIOLOGY. It says that if you take your time, energy and money into getting a university degree then you're supposed to be rewarded ACCORDINGLY.

Interviewer: Uh Huh?

Anecia: Going to HEART according to Christina does not take as much. It doesn't take any money just the government's money(Ah), but it does take your time but not as much time as you would put into your degree so they think we should actually be rewarded accordingly.

Interviewer: Have you ever been to a mechanic shop

Group: Yes

Interviewer: Have you ever seen a price list there

Group: Yes..No (chorus of yes and no)

Rhonda: Some of us are of the perception that after we complete our degree and we graduate from whatever university then we are of the perception that we are supposed to automatically awarded a managerial position and we do not understand and we have to work our way from the top up (group interjects “from the bottom up”) yes from the bottom up. I’m sorry, but employers don’t just seek out academics but experience in the area so, I went ahead to get a skill so as to not have myself out of a job when I leave school.

Interviewer: Do you think vocational courses are adequately promoted to kids whether they are slow or bright?

Group: Yes! Yes!

Interviewer: What’s your name?

Respondent: Khalia

Interviewer: Harrison right?

Khalia: Yes

Interviewer: Do you think vocational courses are adequately promoted to kids. Now say for instance, do you have a child Khalia?

Khalia: No (group laughs)

Interviewer: I’m just asking ah, would you allow your child to choose whether its becoming a cook or electrician versus going to university.

Khalia: Of course Sir! It depends because if they are good at doing stuff like that then no problem she can go ahead because what if she can go ahead because what if he or she is not inclined to do (group interjects “he or she”), he or she is not inclined to do bookwork per se then it makes no sense. So if she wants to do that then fine, go ahead

Interviewer: When was the last time you saw a HEART advertisement?

Group: Mumbles (*looks puzzled*).

Anecia: Can’t tell when last I don’t watch TV often.

Garcia: Actually HEART, it is promoted to both intellectual smart people and those not because there are people with a lot of subjects going into HEART now. I myself experienced that when I was going to HEART, A LOT (*high pitch for emphasis*). Folks in there with eight (8), six (6), seven (7), eight (8) subjects.

Interviewer: And just for the record, what did you do at HEART?

Garcia: Front Office

Rhonda: When I even ask why am I here, they themselves (*high pitch*) are of the perception that persons who are inclined that way (them and us aura) should not be here. But they ask, why am I here (*referring to persons with multiple subjects questioning their motives of being qualified but enrolled at HEART (why am I here)*).

Interviewer: Oh they ask that

Rhonda: Yes

Interviewer: Ok

Rhonda: Yes, why am I here with nine (9) subjects.

- Christina:** The issue with children is that ah, vocational studies seems to be a back up for academic, so only if you fail at academic then yeah you're given a chance to do vocation.
- Interviewer:** If you were supposed to promote it what message would you send out? How would you promote it?
- Group:** Promote vocation?
- Interviewer:** Promote vocation training
- Anecia:** The first thing you'd do is to highlight, I guess would be the money (*aristocratic tone*) cause I don't know that its not as low paying and as menial as we thought so I figure that's basically the first thing I...
- Interviewer:** Mr. Man (Jon Hudson)
- Jon:** Well I like the perception of the general public.
- Interviewer:** Well that's what I'm trying to do right here. I'm trying to get your perception.
- Jon:** Because most people might think, saying that to do the vocational thing might be, maybe under (*gesticulates with hands displaying vocational education as low*). Or looked from a different perspective or different angle from being at a university.
- Interviewer:** (*scenario*) There is a young lady in in Cayman right now. What she did, she's from Jamaica, she always wanted to do mechanics. Now she did it the sophisticated way by going to Canada, getting a bachelors then a masters and with mechanics there's a whole heap of qualifications like MSP. She's now a big manager for a roads agency. Now she's still vocational because as a big manager she's still required to give her expertise but she doesn't really get her hands dirty. But she's vocational because that's whats at the basis of her competence.
- Neocorla:** Well I wouldn't consider that
- Interviewer:** Why not
- Neocorla:** Because, normally my perception of vocational is dirty. So if you don't get your hands dirty, then technically its not vocation.

END OF FOCUS GROUP #1

Interview Example

Interview # 3

- Interviewer:** So I'm gonna start with ahh...what's your name?
- Respondent:** Owen Bennett
- Interviewer:** Which course are you in Owen?
- Owen:** M.I.S which is management information systems
- Interviewer:** Alright, Owen now, what's your career goal?
- Owen:** I'd like to be a business systems analyst.
- Interviewer:** How long you've had this career goal?

Owen: Well, basically I've been I ahh...numerous computer courses already cause I did a CCT course here before and now I'm doing an MIS course, and I think business courses attracts me also, computer courses also.

Interviewer: Owen, what factors led you to choosing this course, why did you choose this course?

Owen: As I said before its basically a mixture of business and computing and I think it's a very good start seeing that I want to become a business systems analyst.

Interviewer: Have you ever seen yourself doing a vocational type of course whether it's a farmer, or barber, mechanic, mason, carpenter...

Owen: Well would you class a computer technician as a vocational course?

Interviewer: To an extent it is

Owen: Well yes, I've seen myself in a vocational course.

Interviewer: Taking computer technician out of it, something else

Owen: Does it have anything to do with computers

Interviewer: So basically you love computers?

Owen: Yes, I love computers.

Interviewer: Did anyone influence your current career choice?

Owen: Yes. A lot of persons for example my first teacher, when I came to Montego Bay Community College. He taught me HTML and technician, technical things about the computer and from there on, I liked it. Cause when I was going to high school, computer was not really...was not really nice.

Interviewer: Alright, back in high school what did you like then?

Owen: Sciences

Interviewer: Ok and it...computing was not as nice then in terms of sciences what do you think you would have become?

Owen: Well I wanted to become a scientist. Basically is either a biologist or physicist.

Interviewer: Why?

Owen: Cause I like the reason. I like to solve problems and I like the...the... its very fascinating to learn new things and about the function of the human body and the whole ecosystem on a whole.

Interviewer: You've considered being a doctor?

Owen: ahh... Doctor yes, but not as much as being a scientist. I'd rather being a specific not a general scientist.

Interviewer: Ok, were your parents influential in your current choice?

Respondent: Yes, they're influential so if I wanted to do something they'd influence me more to do it and find means and ways to encourage me to pursue it?

Interviewer: Ok, you have a genie right here; you have a lamp right here. You rub the side of the lamp and the genie pops and gives you one wish. Now what would you want to become with a snap of a finger?

Owen: I would like to own my own computing business.

Interviewer: Why?

Owen: Because I love computers, again, and I think I'm more of a business person, in Jamaican terms, a hustler. Well and I believe if you have money you can have anything physical.

Interviewer: Money, so say if computer technician as a vocational course if it paid a lot would you go into that course?

Owen: Yes, I would go into it.

Interviewer: Ok, what happen to car diagnostics, car diagnostics have a computer aspect to it and some would term it as almost mechanical cause you're still a mechanical engineer. Would you go into that if it paid a lot?

Owen: Yes, I would! As long as it has to do with Information Technology, I would. For example, I would like to earn a business...I would like to won a business that creates systems for organizations. To make sure that organizations run properly and efficiently with no glitches. To have that business own more money by its own...on its own

Interviewer: Are you driven by the passion for computers or money which one?

Owen: Well, everybody would say money, but basically it's a mixture of both. If I tell you one of them, I wouldn't be telling the truth. But I love computers and everybody loves money
(laughs)

Interviewer: Ok, yes we're now in the computer age or the digital age but if it paid minimum wage would you still do it?

Owen: No! I wouldn't do it. Ahh...I would do it in terms of a side by thing for example if...computers is paying more now but...I'd also like to do a little bit of graphic design and graphic design doesn't pay as mush as what I really want to do...

Interviewer: Alright, fair enough. What perceptions do you have about people who do vocational education?

Owen: Well, I think they're needed because without them we wont have the higher class cause we do them as classes right...without the lower class we cant have a higher class because we need them to uplift the higher class. Cause if you're a manager, who's going to work for you if you don't have a lower class.

Interviewer: I'm glad you said that, why is vocational education seen as as lower class versus a doctor seen as a higher class?

Owen: I'm going to give an answer that is socially correct.

Interviewer: Ok.

Owen: When you're studying to be a doctor right, you have to learn everything. There is not just basics, its everything in detail, in depth. You have to know where its coming from, is it going, to give you the side effects. While if you're a nurse, you don't need to know every, single thing. You just need to know a basic, the needs of what the doctor would require and how to do...My next point is, you really have to spend more time on the next night...not only that, you have to do more work than the other. The higher class, wont do as much work as the vocational, but in terms of knowing, understanding they have to know that if there's a mistake, I am the one who's responsible for it because I'm the one who's supposed to know this.

Vocational persons, they're supposed to know it, but not to an extent that you should (the doctor). One has more responsibility.

Interviewer: Alright, a university degree or HEART certificate or HEART competence, which one do you think has more prestige?

Owen: (*arrogant sigh*) Well, that question answers itself. A university degree of course.

Interviewer: Ok, why the fact that when I go to HEART why does society not see me as being similar to a man in a suit with a brief case?

Owen: That's because society, well that would be a sociology question, but let me give you my input, my input is, they class the work that you're studying for, they're gonna class you.

Interviewer: Ok, what do you think accounts for the difference, why is there a difference?

Owen: Why is there a difference? As I said before, money, right. First of all if yuh go study fi do sup'm wha nah give yuh nuff money, nuff prestige y'nah go to it. First of all if you're going to study for something that will not earn a lot of money or prestige then you definitely will not do it. If you look at any career, right, if the career itself nah give (not giving) as much money as others, it's not recognized much, it's not given much prestige as any other career. But if it gives you a good pay, but not maximum pay, yeah, you'll recognize it.

Interviewer: Ok, ahh... when was the last to you saw a HEART advertisement?

Owen: Well, to tell you the truth, I don't watch local television a lot. But I heard... I see it on billboards and I've seen a few things on the internet when I'm browsing. Cause when I was looking for a college to go to I was looking at various...

Interviewer: Which high school did you attend?

Owen: Hebert Morrison

Interviewer: Perfect, now in terms of prestige, do you think there's a difference between how people see Cornwall College and Herbert Morrison?

Owen: In my days, yes.

Interviewer: Just for the record, Hebert Morrison is Hebert Morrison Technical High School.

Owen: Yes, Hebert Morrison Technical High School.

Interviewer: Why do you think people see them as different?

Owen: Cause, one, what they usually say is that Cornwall usually get more, ahh... persons who is in the Higher Society now usually come from Cornwall and Cornwall is not a technical high school, right. So most things that are vocational are technical. Cornwall is more of a prestige in terms of if you want to become Lawyers and stuff, not...it doesn't really focus on technicality and as we're doing this study right now, Hebert Morrison would fall in that category of technical. (*Turn Tape*). Yes as I said before, Herbert Morrison is basically a technical high school and most vocational jobs are technical.

Interviewer: Do you think there's sort of an academic discrimination, meaning, do you think it's a brighter or duncer or the slower go to either schools?

Owen: Never! To tell you the truth, usually persons will ask that question. My parents usually ask, why you don't want to go a Compre (Hebert Morrison Technical High School formerly Comprehensive High School so Compre for short) why you want to go to Cornwall or why don't you want to go Cornwall or Compre. It's not about passes cause...since recently for the

record...I looked in a Gleaner and I see the subject passes for the 2006 up until 2008 and in terms of technical high school, Hebert Morrison is at the top of that list. Discrimination...

Interviewer: Ok Owen, I'm going to make you my marketing manager. How would you promote vocational training?

Owen: If I want young persons, it's young persons in my advertisements. To catch young persons find out what...what the young one need, what attracts the young persons.

Interviewer: What attracts you?

Owen: What attracts me?

Interviewer: Uh huh

Owen: I like vibes, partying, hype. It must be exciting it must not be boring it nuffi be a long lecture. (It must not be a long lecture). That's why when it come to, for example you're going to...be able to drive this car...alright mechanic, when you're fixing this care you're gonna be able to test the engine...to rev it out and them stuff deh. We're gonna work on this type of car, we're gonna be able topull aprt an engine and put it back together and see how it works. Yeah! Fine, Bring it, I'm in!

END OF INTERVIEW

Appendix F
Identification of Meaning Unit Categories

Focus Group # 1

1) Question: What courses do you consider to be Vocational?

Group: (Group Mumbling) Architecture, Engineering, Food and Nutrition, Food Prep.

Group: Yeah and Cosmo Tech (Cosmetology).

2) Question: What are your perceptions of vocational Education

Insufficient Remuneration

Tiffany: It nuh degrading but no money nuh deh pon it. *(Its not degrading but it doesn't pay well)*

Unequal pay with non-vocational programmes

Sanjae: On the pay and the work you have to put in because I'm now doing a litt...I would say bookwork and it's very hard. **If I could go to HEART and get...lets say more money (high pitch for emphasis) than what I'm going to get now then sure I'd (high pitch for emphasis) do it!*

Lacks the Ability for Vocational Programmes

Garcia: I'm not good at hair so...

Garcia: Ahh! I could but if I was going to do like Chemistry, but I don't like Chemistry therefore, I'm not going to go to school for it.

Recreational

Garcia: Yes but not as a day job.

Garcia: Cause that's not my area (laughs) I didn't want to do it I just wanted to do it for fun.

Back up or last Option

Christina: The issue with children is that ah, vocational studies seems to be a back up for academic, so only if you fail at academic then yeah you're given a chance to do vocation.

Dirty Jobs

Neocorla: Because, normally my perception of vocational is dirty. So if you don't get your hands dirty, then technically its not vocation.

3) Who do you think these courses are more suited for?

Not for women (Gendered Perceptions)

Natasha: Males.

Rhonda: (with the help of group) Its sweaty, the floor everything that's not lady- like. Technically, that's not me.

For those who lack literary skills or qualifications for progression

Anecia: No, No! It's not about the gender, or whatever but I think it's for **people who lacks Subjects, lacks literary skills.**

Persons good with their hands and technical skills

Rhonda: Like, the main reason why HEART was developed was geared towards persons who are not dunce but persons who were good with their hands. So they are more able to

express themselves that way and they have good technical skills so therefore more able to advance.

4) Which professions do you see as ideal?

Esteem of non-vocational jobs

Mario: The Lawyers and the Doctors are generally who people look up to so like in society **they have a higher standard.**

5) What do you honestly think of manual or non-office careers like vocational courses?

Based on Strength

Jon: It's based on strength.

Laborious

Anecia: Labour intensive.

Garcia: HA! To stand up on my foot with a 16 hour day and damaging my fingers (*high pitch tone for emphasis*) (alluding to cosmetology).

i) What if you owned the salon?

Preference for Entrepreneurship

Garcia: If I owned the salon (*strong tone*) , I'd be employing (*strong tone*) people to work.

Preference for Office Comfort

Garcia: Exactly! (*strong tone*) So I'd be in the OFFICE (*high tone*) under AC watching them do MY WORK. (Group: Laughs)

6) What do you think accounts for the difference between a university education and the education from HEART?

Society's Standards

Anecia: Society's Standards!

Uneven post-qualification rewards

Christina: SOCIOLOGY-BASED, its me, how we start off again? If we make the choice of going to university that's like going spending my time and money to go to university. I want to benefit from that but if I'm going to HEART, you don't pay much money and things like that. I don't think (pause) you're going to get the same amount of pay. You don't get the same amount of pay.

7) Do you think vocational courses are adequately promoted?

Not Promoted Well

Khalia: **NO! (*Group laughs*) **

Promoted well and to Different Academic Levels

Garcia: Actually HEART, it is promoted to both intellectual smart people and those not because there are people with a lot of subjects going into HEART now. I myself experienced that when I was going to HEART, A LOT (*high pitch for emphasis*). Folks in there with eight (8), six (6), seven (7), eight (8) subjects.

8) How would you promote it (Vocational Training)?

Highlight income potential

Anecia: The first thing you'd do is to highlight, I guess would be the money (*aristocratic tone*) cause I don't know that its not as low paying and as menial as we thought so I figure that's basically the first thing I...

Change perception of Public-Image Building

Jon: Well I like the perception of the general public.

Jon: Because most people might think, saying that to do the vocational thing might be, **maybe under** (*gesticulates with hands displaying vocational education as low*). Or looked from a different perspective or different angle from being at a university.

Interview# 1

1) What perceptions do you have about people who do vocational education?

Class Distinctions

Owen: Well, I think they're needed because without them we wont have the higher class cause we do them as classes right...without the lower class we cant have a higher class because we need them to uplift the higher class. Cause if you're a manager, who's going to work for you if you don't have a lower class.

2) Why is vocational education seen as as lower class versus a doctor seen as a higher class?

Vocational students are less knowledgeable

Vocational careers are more laborious

Vocational careers are given less responsibility

Owen: When you're studying to be a doctor right, you have to learn everything. There is... its not just basics, its everything in detail, in depth. You have to know where its coming from, is it going, to give you the side effects. While if you're a nurse, you don't need to know every, single thing. You just need to know a basic, the needs of what the doctor would require and how to do...My next point is, you really have to spend more time on the next night...not only that, you have to do more work than the other. The higher class, wont do as much work as the vocational, but in terms of knowing, understanding they have to know that if there's a mistake, I am the one who's responsible for it because I'm the one who's supposed to know this. Vocational persons, they're supposed to know it, but not to an extent that you should (the doctor). One has more responsibility.

3) What do you think accounts for the difference between university education and vocational programmes?

Difference in income

Courses are chosen based on prestige

Unrecognizable qualifications

Programme stereotypes

Owen: Why is there a difference? As I said before, money, right. First of all if yuh go study fi do sup'm wha nah give yuh nuff money, nuff prestige y'nah go to it. First of all if you're going to study for something that will not earn a lot of money or prestige then you definitely will not do it. If you look at any career, right, if the career itself nah give (not giving) as much money as others, it's not recognized much, it's not given much prestige as any other career.

4) Is there a difference in perception in how people view Cornwall College versus Hebert Morrison Technical High School?

i) Why do you think people see them as different?

Social class prejudices

More prestige in non-vocational institutions

Institutional class distinctions

Owen: Cause, one, what they usually say is that Cornwall usually get more, ahh... persons who is in the Higher Society now usually come from Cornwall and Cornwall is not a technical high school, right. So most things that are vocational are technical. **Cornwall is more of a prestige in terms of if you want to become Lawyers and stuff, not...it doesn't really focus on technicality** and as we're doing this study right now, Hebert Morrison would fall in that category of technical. (*Turn Tape*). Yes as I said before, Herbert Morrison is basically a technical high school and most vocational jobs are technical.

5) How would you promote vocational training?

Customize the promotional campaign to meet the target group

Owen: If I want young persons, it's young persons in my advertisements. To catch young persons find out what...what the young one need, what attracts the young persons.

6) What attracts you?

Up-tempo promotions

Highlight exciting activities

Owen: I like vibes, partying, hype. It must be exciting it must not be boring it nuffi be a long lecture. (It must not be a long lecture). That's why when it come to, for example you're going to...be able to drive this car...alright mechanic, when you're fixing this care you're gonna be able to test the engine...to rev it out and them stuff deh. **We're gonna work on this type of car, we're gonna be able to pull apart an engine and put it back together and see how it works. Yeah! Fine, Bring it, I'm in!**

Appendix G: Summarization of Individual Transcripts

FOCUS GROUPS

Focus Group #1

The members from Focus Group#1 gave vivid testimonies of their feelings and perceptions of vocational training. From their accounts thirteen meaning unit categories emerged with monetary compensation and remuneration being the most glaring concern. The group also believed that even though these disciplines were not degrading, it was the perceived low pay that caused the disinterest. The group also felt that this arm of education was suited for students with low aptitude and little literary skills. There was also a perceived distinction in the parity of esteem between university based professions and vocational careers. It is also important to note that the group considers Jamaica's Human Employment and Resource Training (HEART) institutions as being synonymous with vocational training. This means that the group was probably totally oblivious to the fact that they too are students of a vocational institution and in a vocational programme.

Focus Group #3

Focus Group #3 provided the most glaring accounts of the relevance of income potential in education. Eventual remuneration of non-vocational professions versus vocational trades were the primary meaning unit categories expressed by this group. So much was the importance of this category that it was intertwined with all other meaning unit category. The general perception was that vocational education and careers did not pay as much as other professions and to them this was important. Members were also assertive in this claim as vividly seen in the following excerpt "Money, Money, Money it's the final deal!" Some were also considered engaging in unethical practices such as smuggling because the potential for huge economic rewards were more likely. The other perceptions that emerged was that vocational education a last resort option. They felt that vocational education and careers should only be entered into if nothing else worked out and it was also seen as a lack of ambition or a sign of low aspiration if they or their offspring ventured into this discipline. Complimenting this notion was the fact that vocational careers and education were thought of as "settling" in that, if you had the ability to do otherwise you should.

INTERVIEWS

Unlike the aforementioned focus group interviews, the semi-structured one-one interviews provided richer and more intimate testimonies that had multiple perceptions in each meaning unit category.

Interview #1

The social perceptions and caste consciousness were the primary categories emerging from this interview. Christopher believed that vocational programmes were more appropriate for students enrolled in Comprehensive Schools. However, if you had a practical mindset or the "mind to do it", you could still enroll in it. He alluded to the social distinctions between academic-based professions and vocational careers and thought that the society's perceptions helped to perpetuate such perceptions. He felt that the society stigmatized

vocational programmes and “looked down” on the careers that they prepared for. In addition, Christopher also felt that jobs and professions were class-specific. He believed that the “higher class” would assume positions like lawyers and doctors whereas it was typical for the ‘grassroot’ level favouring vocational trades like masons and mechanics”. In other words there was a level of caste consciousness in how roles and jobs were perceived. He also felt that professions like doctors and lawyers carried a higher degree of esteem than vocational trades and as such were more prestigious.

The other meaning unit categories unearthed from this interview related to gendered perceptions, dirtiness and the perceived disparity between qualifications. Christopher believed that mostly male gravitated to vocational programmes and many of the careers offered in this discipline were perceived as dirty. He also felt that vocational qualifications were lesser in value and unrecognized than that of academic accolades.

Christopher was however quick to highlight the positives of vocational education and careers. He believed that vocational students were more rounded and were able to “turn them hand mek fashion” which in the Jamaican context meant they were creative and resourceful. He also expressed that while non-vocational careers like doctors and lawyers underwent the time consuming hassle of medical schools and law schools, vocational skills could be learnt quickly and thus would start earning money quicker.

Interview #2

Tamoy felt that vocational careers were time consuming but suited for anyone who liked it. She believed there were several advantages of vocational programmes such as providing the opportunity to make money as well as apply your skills overseas. However, she felt that the society’s perception of vocational careers and qualifications were uneven thus attaining the latter would make it “harder to get a job”. It was also felt that vocational qualifications did not fit the typical progression of the education system. Hence schools that offered vocational qualifications did not fit into society’s perception of the true route to success and upward mobility. There were also important themes that had to be deduced from Tamoy’s body language, attitude and manner in which she gave certain descriptions. Based on observation and attitude, Tamoy’s attitude was dissociative when asked whether she would enroll in vocational education. She also confirmed this when off the record; she wanted little to do or associated with vocational programmes

Interview #3

Owen’s testimony and descriptions painted a detail picture of the vocational perceptions that exist. He believed that vocational students that go on to vocational careers are of the lower class. This was vivid in his statement which stated that “I think they are needed because without them we would not have a higher class”. Apart from caste differences, Owen believed they were less trained and “had to do more work” than non-vocational professions. Like most of the other interviews, he agreed that there were differences in prestige and future earnings with vocational trades earning considerably less than other professions. In addition, prestige was another feature that was not typical of vocational qualification and careers He also believed that there was a disparity between vocational qualifications and more academic qualifications. This was expressed this by stating that vocational qualifications were “not recognized”. Additionally, Owen posited that society classed students based on the courses they chose which meant that there were education had different stereotypes and these stereotypes influenced students enrollment choices. Throughout his testimonies, there was a high sense of caste consciousness where he believed that society was stratified. He thought that there were institutional class differences with students of the lower class attending Technical pro-vocational high schools while upper class students attended the traditional high schools that taught mostly theoretic university-bound subjects.

Interview #4

The perceptions that emerged from Lawrence's interview include: uneven qualifications and the perceived parity of importance. He believed that society favoured academic qualifications and once "you were doing a degree; you were seen as doing something more important than a mere certificate". Additionally, he felt that vocational certificates did not hold the same prestige as degrees and were not as recognized as universities.

Interview #5

Four meaning unit categories emanated from Jason's descriptions. He felt that vocational subjects were for students who were without the requisite qualifications to progress. However, he believed that the discipline was for anyone once they had the "drive" for it. Jason noted that potential students opted to enroll in universities because it was believed that it "offered better opportunities". They would also detour from vocational qualifications because in these programmes they don't usually get the remuneration commensurate of their worth and workload.

Appendix H: Project Proposal and Ethics Form

Appendix H					
Project Proposal					
Electronic AGC FORM (PROPOSAL)					
SECTION 1: STUDENT TO COMPLETE					
NAME:	Ewort Atkinson	I.D. No:	059XXX934	ENROLMENT/START DATE (mm/yy):	April 2006
PROGRAMME:	MBA	MODULE:	THE PROPOSAL	LOCAL RESOURCE CENTRE	EFA Jamaica
STUDENT DECLARATION: In submitting work to the University you are agreeing to the following statement: "I declare that this assignment is my own work, that all sources of					
SECTION 2: TUTOR'S COMMENTS					
Ability to construct a project with clear, coherent and well defended research questions/ objectives					
Discussion of the relation between your proposed research and previous research					
Discussion and justification of proposed methods					
Overall Comments:					

**School of Management Dissertation
Proposal Pro-Forma
Version 1.2 (August 2008)**

Section 1: The Proposal Template

Your Name, Programme of Study, Student Number, Centre & Intake. Ewort Mark Atkinson, MBA, 059xxx934, EFA – Jamaica- April 2006

Please identify any University of Leicester Tutors with whom you have discussed your proposal and the forum you used (e.g. workshops/Blackboard) Dr. Danziel Nurdilek (Blackboard)

Title Understanding the role of image building in the education industry: A study of the image and perceptions associated with Applied Education/Vocational Training
--

Abstract (max. 200 words)

Vocational Training or Applied Education as it is now called has the potential to yield many benefits, the most important being the expansion of career options for young people and adults in the Cayman Islands. However, even with its apparent advantages, Applied Education is rarely seen as a premier choice for students.

The aim of this proposal is to identify whether the image or perception associated with Applied Education is responsible for this lack of interest, and if so, how understanding these perceptions can contribute to image building. The study will fulfill its aims by using primarily qualitative research methods to find out how much knowledge is known about vocational training; the perceptions associated with Applied Education; what are the suggested ways of promoting this arm of education and how will this knowledge assist in promoting the image of Applied Education. Quantitative data will also be used minimally to provide enrollment and graduation statistics. When completed the study would have illuminated the wider perceptions associated with Applied Education and also confirm or deny if image/perception is the cause for lack of interest in Applied Education.

Introduction

The research will draw on many academic studies including *Promote the Vocational Program* by Karen Quinn. Quinn highlighted that the greatest stigma concerning vocational training is found within the school itself and the community (Quinn, 1981). Consequently, the main research question will be to highlight the image associated with vocational training in the high schools and the community and to see whether image/perception currently plays a role in the lack of interest in Applied Education. The sub-questions are:

1. What is the public's perception of Applied/Vocational Education?
2. Does the perception of Applied Education pose a threat to its image building?
3. What are the preferred career options for students and parents and why?
4. What is the general consensus on the best ways of promoting Applied Education and how can these promotional insights lead to image building?
5. What if any are the changes needed to promote this discipline and how can these promotional insights contribute to image building?

Personal Interest

The concept of promoting Applied Education (Vocational Training) has been a passion of mine since youth. I believe that the intellectual capacity to become Lawyers, Doctors Accountants etc is only possessed by a few. Consequently, career options that require less aptitude should be seen as being just as important in society as the other heavily sought after professions.

Relation to previous research

The academic work of Quinn was assessed to see if her study, methods and findings were similar and applicable to the Cayman context. To deviate from her methodology, I'll attempt to use Participatory Learning and Action (PLA) techniques to provide a more comfortable outlet where respondents will hopefully provide accurate answers. This will help me to assess whether there really is a negative perception associated with vocational education and also unearth any the issues that may be relevant.

Many of the perceptions that are associated with Vocational Training have been based on ideals passed on within the home. Susan Peckham in her article entitled *Technically Speaking* states that most parents want their kids to complete four years of college and find white collar jobs because careers like line technicians and welders is not seen as cool or ambitious anymore (Peckham, S. 2007). In fact, Marie Owens head of Communications at Middlesex University in her bid to promote vocational training noted that the UK have a history of not wanting their children to become plumbers or electricians but rather to attend four year colleges. These sentiments are similar worldwide and being a colony of the United Kingdom, Cayman also shares these views. The rationale is simple; there is a marked distinction between the perceptions associated with four year college education versus a discipline that requires little intellectual aptitude for matriculation.

Image and image building are therefore the key aspects that must be understood if Applied Education is to loose its stigmatic perceptions. According to W. Reynolds in his article 'The role of the Consumer in Image Building', image must be studied based on several considerations including the notion of Belief versus Fact. This consideration stated that the initial belief about a product or brand (whether true or false) can lead to dozens of other beliefs (Reynolds, W. 1965). In other words, just by seeing a red apple, one starts to infer or believe that it is juicy, sweet, etc. It's also similarly with jobs and in education. A man that wears a tailored suit will be perceived as being well paid, works in an office and drives a nice car versus a mechanic who is greasy, dirty and reeks of engines, the latter undoubtedly will be viewed as broke and over-worked. Moreover, these perceptions are passed on from generation to generation and consumer to consumer. The solution therefore is to understand the underlying perceptions of vocational training, how familiar is the target group with this discipline and then promote this arm of education by dispelling these perceptions. In truth, marketers can achieve success in this education by dispelling these perceptions. In truth, marketers can achieve success in this is of a certain class and then stand back and watch customers draw inferences and spread the word (Reynolds, W. 1965). Promoting Applied Education is relatively similar.

Proposed methods

Primary Data Collection

Questionnaires, interviews and focus group discussion will form the basis of the primary data collection. Questionnaires will be created in a concise, easy to read format which will be given to a wide cross-section of students and communities within the Cayman Islands. Additionally, teachers and industry professionals within the applied education industry will be interviewed in order to gather their views on how vocational education can be better promoted. Since the primary target group will encompass secondary and post secondary individuals, all interviews, questionnaires and other data collecting methods will be done in a fashion that is simple and uses only the basic lexicon.

The study will also use Participatory Learning and Action (PLA techniques), a community development approach whereby facilitators work with communities to help them analyze their needs, identify solutions to fill those needs and develop and implement a plan of action (Anonymous 2008) This approach is ideal for the close knit Caymanian community as it can be used to help expand the initial answers proposed by citizens.

Secondary Data Collection

Secondary information will be collected primarily from online journals, in particular, *The Journal of Vocational Education and Research*. Additional information will be attained through books, magazines, news articles, digital libraries and the Internet. One key online source will be the Cayman Islands statistical website (www.eso.ky) and this will provide some of the quantitative data needed to substantiate the dissertation.

Data Analysis

To capture and analyse the opinions and views of the respondents, a five point Likert scale questionnaire will be used. With subsequent analysis this will provide useful information on the perceptions of the respondents as well as their views on how they believe Applied Education should be promoted to stimulate interest. Face to Face interaction is also very important since, answers can be elaborated thereby painting a more accurate picture. Hence, interviews, focus groups and Participatory Learning and Action (PLA) approaches will be used to gain information for the analysis of:

- The images associated with vocational education?
- Whether it is felt that vocational education is being promoted favourably.
- The appropriate means promoting applied education in Grand Cayman based on individual recommendations.
- What percentage of the respondents would choose Vocational Education over more academic disciplines and what would stimulate their decision

In addition to the qualitative analysis, the project will also use quantitative means of assessment. This will come in the form of viewing and analyzing key employment and labour statistics to highlight whether there is a demand in the educational system calling for the development and promotion of applied education.

Reflections (approx. 500 words)

Throughout the course of this dissertation two concerns may emerge, the limited secondary resources in Grand Cayman and the flexibility that will be approved by the government. The former will be resolved by conducting research at the University of the West Indies (Jamaica). Additional costs will not be incurred due to the frequency of planned travel already scheduled between both territories. In addition, full use will be made of key online sources that relate to the proposed subject matter such as the Journal of Vocational Education and Research. As for the second concern, prior to engaging in any activity, adequate approval will be sought from the appropriate government officials. If an activity is not granted

Conceptual framework and Theoretical Problems and Difficulties

Due to the demographics and the close knit social landscape of the Cayman Islands gaining information can become difficult especially if the researcher is not familiar to the community. The islands are diverse and though the English Language is the main form of communication, research will have to be cognizant of other languages and dialects. Additionally, it is envisioned that citizens may become suspicious and apprehensive if they aren't sure the reason for the data being collected. Consequently, the solution is to make alliances with persons who are familiar with these communities; a move that is already done. If alliance is not sought the information may become questionable as respondents may have little motivation to comply and so lie to appease the interviewer.¹

Ethics

Ethics has to be given the highest priority as it is a serious issue in the Cayman Islands. Any perceived breaches of information laws may affect the outcome or completion of the dissertation. Therefore, to gain access to information whether primary or secondary, adequate approval will be given in lieu of interviews and distributing questionnaires. In addition, the intended research individuals or groups will be given the option of anonymity if

they so choose. A strict adherence to objectivity will be maintained and if interviews are taped, all data will be transcribed accurately and re-confirmed with the respondent. Permission will also be requested from parents prior to approaching minors.

Political Field

As a civil servant how information is collected and disseminated is a serious issue. To acquire government endorsement, this dissertation will be submitted to my immediate superior who will then filter it through the appropriate approving channels for review. This superior who will then filter it through the appropriate approving channels for review. This will be done prior to the submission of the intended dissertation. The fate of this research topic is however very favorable, since it is hoped that the findings revealed will assist in promoting not just applied education but also a useful framework to promote other aspects of education.

Conclusion

Like every facet of marketing, image and perception are important factors that can stimulate or dissuade buyer action. The education industry is no different. For a marketer to promote Applied Education or any aspect of education, they must first understand the perception associated with these disciplines. They must then customize their marketing campaigns to manage these perceptions. Understanding the perceptions associated with Applied Education will first entail researching and sorting all the relevant information and academic discourses that addresses image building, vocational training and the varied perceptions of education. However, the most pressing action that is first required is the familiarization of research intentions by superiors after which I will continue gathering the data that will facilitate my Literature Review. Subsequently, I intend to brainstorm possible questions for my questionnaire forms, focus groups and Participatory Learning and Action exercise. After conducting all the relevant research methodologies I will attempt to prove that perceptions and image plays a vital role in promoting service industries like education. Therefore, for less popular programmes like vocational training to be promoted successfully, it has to identify whether its image is contributing to its lack of acceptance and if so, will require image building considerations.

Timetable

The ensuing chart shows a detailed time schedule for the management and completion of this dissertation. However, the proposed schedule may change if contingents occur.

- September 2008 | Submission of Proposal
- December 2008 | Sourcing Data: Literature and references search
- January 2009 | Literature Review
- February 2009 | Questionnaire Distribution and Focus Group interviews
- March 2009 | Analysis of Data
- April 2009 | Sorting and Sifting Data
- May – June 2009 | Writing chapters
- June – July | Perusal by key government officials
- July 2009 | Final review and tweaking Data
- August 2009 | Submission of the Dissertation |

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Section 2: University of Leicester School of Management - Initial Ethical Review Form

Leicester University School of Management Ethical Review Form: Part 1

Please read the following two statements and place an X in the area indicated for the statement that most accurately represents your research intentions. | Student Statement. | Insert X | Student Action. | | :--- | :---: | :--- |
| Statement 1 | I have read the above information. I confirm that my research *does not* involve the study of live human beings. | | You do not need to complete Part 2 of this form. Ethics approval is *not* required. | | Statement 2 | I have read the above information. I confirm that my research *does* involve the study of live human beings. | X |
Please proceed to complete Part 2 of this form. |

Leicester University School of Management Ethical Review Form: Part 2

Please answer all of these questions by ticking yes or no in the box provided

1. Does the study involve participants who are particularly vulnerable or unable to give informed consent? (e.g. people under the age of 18, people with learning disabilities, students you teach or assess) | | |
2. Will it be necessary for participants to take part in the study without their knowledge and consent at the time? | | |
3. Does the study involve audio or visual recording of people in public places? | | |
4. Will the study involve the discussion of sensitive topics? (e.g. sexual activity, drug use, illegal activities, death, whistleblowing) | | |
5. Are drugs, placebos or other substances to be given to the study participants or will the study involve invasive, intrusive or potentially harmful procedures of any kind? | | |
6. Will blood or tissue samples be obtained from participants? | | |
7. Is physical pain or psychological stress from the proposed project likely to cause harm or negative consequences beyond the risks in normal life? | | |
8. Will the study involve prolonged or repetitive testing? | | |
9. Will financial inducements (other than expenses) be offered to participants? | | |
10. Will the study involve recruitment of patients or staff through the NHS? | | |

If your answer is yes to any of these questions, please fill in Part 3.

Leicester University School of Management Ethical Review Form: Part 3

In no more than a page –

1. Explain why you ticked yes to one or more of the questions on Part 2, and how you plan to address the ethical issues raised.

You will need to do this in consultation with a Dissertation Tutor on Blackboard. Please identify which Tutor you discussed these issues with.

Blackboard Tutor's Name: Dr. Danziel Nurdilek

The aim of the research is to understand the role of image building in the education industry. It will aim to identify the perceptions associated with vocational education and to achieve this the study will entail the participation of various age ranges in the Educational system in particularly 15 – 25 years old. Minors will be used because they represent the group that is either at the initial stages of their career decisions, have not yet made career choices or totally clueless of what they'll do in the future. Therefore, it is essential that questionnaires be given to these groups as they will offer an ideal insight into what they'll be choosing, why and whether their decisions are directed or independent. Hence, in order to extrapolate the required information from these respondents, questionnaires will be given as well as focus group discussion. In addition, as

mentioned in the proposal, permission will be sought from parents prior to any researched based communication.

My reason for ticking yes in question#1 is due to the likelihood of minors (under 18) participating in the study. To adhere to the essence of ethics I intend to seek permission from parents and/or teachers before embarking on any research. I also intend to use the most basic level of the lexicon to ensure the minors are aware of what is being asked.

Assessor's Comments (to be completed by the markers of the proposal)

Assessor's Name: Assessor's Signature: Date:

¹ Swetnam, D. (2001). *Write your own Dissertation: How to prepare and Present Successful Work*. How to Books Limited.

Author's Note

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I wrote this thesis in 2010 as part of the requirements for my MBA at the University of Leicester. The study was conducted using student samples from Jamaica and the Cayman Islands, including cooperative students from the Montego Bay Community College.

At the time, the perception of education pathways was relatively fixed. Academic routes were widely regarded as the standard for success, while vocational and applied education were viewed as secondary options. This study examined those perceptions and the role of image building in shaping them.

Since then, the labour market has evolved significantly. The increasing pace of technological change, particularly with the rise of artificial intelligence, has accelerated shifts in how work is structured and valued. While AI has not replaced work entirely, it has intensified the need for continuous reskilling and adaptability.

We are now in an environment where job functions are constantly evolving. Estimates suggest that a significant portion of existing roles will be disrupted, while new ones continue to emerge. This has increased the relevance of skilled, applied roles typically associated with TVET. As noted by Elon Musk, there is a growing global need for electricians, plumbers, and carpenters, in many cases exceeding the demand for traditional degree holders ([Economic Times, 2024](#)).

What makes TVET relevant today is not only its practical nature, but its adaptability. It is structured around applied skills, problem solving, and execution. These are areas where human capability continues to complement, rather than compete directly with, AI. As a result, TVET is increasingly positioned as a more responsive model for the current economy (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2023; IIEP-UNESCO, 2024).

This thesis reflects the perceptions of vocational education at a specific point in time. While the context has evolved, the underlying insights into perception, image, and promotion remain relevant. The study therefore provides a foundation for understanding how TVET can be repositioned, particularly within Caribbean contexts.